

CURRENT VALUES BEHIND THE POLITICS OF MOBILITY

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Author: Ghadir Pourhashem, Tatiana Kováčiková (UNIZA)
Steven Verschuur, Cecilia Sbrolli (OC)

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Public report with the critical review of current values behind the politics of Mobility.

D.3.3 is associated with the REBALNCE Task 3.3 described below.

Description of TASK 3.3 – CURRENT VALUES BEHIND THE POLITICS OF MOBILITY: CRITICAL REVIEW

Task 3.3: Review of the evolution of policy-goals and policy-aims in European political documents and regulations and their relations with the “public interest” of transport and mobility policies in Europe

Subtask 3.3.1: Practices of transport appraisal techniques and policy goals
(Task leader: UNIZA)

This task will focus on a critical review of transport appraisal practices for public projects in the EU member states in order to identify areas of convergence and divergence. State-of-the-art work will be based on an in-depth analysis of existing transport appraisal methods and European mobility decision-making process and regulations. The findings will be used to outline under-researched values for multi-modal transport appraisal beyond the traditional speed-time-price paradigm with the respect for the environmental boundaries and people’s wellbeing perspectives and in alignment with the Transport, Health and Environment Pan-European Programme (THE PEP) and the Green Deal for Europe

Subtask 3.3.2: Investigation on the concept of “public interest”
(Task leader: OC)

This task will explore how the concept of “public interest” is reflected in EU legislation and jurisprudence and review how this concept is used in the context of mobility and transport. Useful examples of the concept of “public interest” from EU Member States may be used, where relevant. By analysing relevant pieces of legislation and case-law, this task will investigate how the fact that a given transport policy is of “public interest” is influenced by the vocabulary, the language, and the underlying logics of economics of the relevant legislation and how the concept of “public interest” played a role during the legislative process. Until very recently, public investment on transport infrastructures and services were assessed in a classic utilitarian way: moving more people, faster, at cheapest cost, brings more profitability. This task will look at today’s context, also in light of the findings of Task 3.2, in order to feed into the study of public interest under EU law as a preparatory work for the final deliverable on regulatory policy guidance.

INTRODUCTION

This section presents the context and scope of the report together with a summary of the structure of this deliverable.

- **Context and Scope**

This report forms Deliverable 3.3 (which is part of Work Package 3 on THE LANGUAGE OF THE PRESENT), aiming at capturing the current European mobility narrative, at describing how well this narrative is embedded in European culture and values; as well as providing a critical analysis of the narrative in view to formulating the 'claim' of the REBALANCE Manifesto. More specifically, Deliverable 3.3 is concerned with the current values behind the politics of mobility and presents a twofold critical review: first, that of transport appraisal practices for public projects in the EU; and second, that exploring how the concept of "public interest" is reflected in EU legislation and jurisprudence with particular emphasis on transport and mobility.

This public report is divided into two sections. The first Section (Task 3.3.1) presents the findings of the investigation on applied methods for transport infrastructure appraisals and mobility decision-making process at the EU and national level. The second Section (Task 3.3.2) focuses on the investigation into how EU policy and legislation have influenced the current mobility culture and, in turn, and how new ideas about public interest can help re-shape the current culture for a more sustainable future.

- **Structure of the document**

Section 1 of this report presents the context and scope of Deliverable 3.3 together with a summary of its structure. Section 1 introduces the EU transport and mobility policies and presents a literature review on European sustainable mobility strategy. The scope of transport infrastructure methods is included in Section 2 together with the presentation of strengths and limitations of each appraisal technique. Section 3 includes an overview of analysis of major impacts of contributors used in transport project appraisal as well as some key characteristics of each impact. The findings from reviewing EU Member States national regulations on transport project assessment are included in Section 4.

In Section 5 the investigated under-researched values for multi-modal transport appraisal at the EU level beyond the traditional speed-time-price paradigm are discussed. In Section 6, a cost-benefit analysis case study applying the social well-being approach is presented. Section 7 analyses the concept of public interest and its role in the European Union legislation in relation to mobility. A summary of the most significant findings regarding both Subtasks 3.3.1 and 3.3.2 is presented in Section 8.

1 EU TRANSPORT AND MOBILITY POLICIES AND REGULATIONS – COMMON ROOTS AND DIVERGENCES

Transport and mobility fall within the scope of services of general economic interest (SGEI)¹, which is a category comprising services of economic utility, subject to public service obligations (which will be discussed more at length in Section 7.5.2 below).

Within the regulatory framework of the European Union, a pivotal norm among the typical sources of law is article 14 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) - which has introduced the possibility for EU institutions to issue regulations concerning principles and conditions related to the functioning of these services, which is in line with the common values of the Union.

With specific regard to transport, EU policy pursues the goal of ensuring an efficient, safe and free movement of people and goods throughout the EU. In line with this purpose, the EU aims to implement intermodal transport in order to constitute an integrated network of transport².

Furthermore, the EU transport policy also includes the fight against climate change with sustainable mobility at its core. In this regard, the EU Climate law proposed by the European Commission is in force for the Member States. The role of mobility is as an asset to the internal market and the quality of life of citizens who enjoy the freedom to travel, as was already done by 2011 White Paper and the EU Green Deal that reiterates the goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 90% within 2050, compared to 1990 levels.

1.1 Urban Mobility in the EU Framework

In 2009 the Commission developed an "Action Plan on Urban Mobility"³, entailing a number of actions centered around six themes.

The Communication reiterates that urban transport is an integrated part of the common EU transport policy. Furthermore, by starting from the fundamental role that urban areas have both from an economic and social point of view, the Commission seeks to outline a series of key targets to address sustainability challenges in the context of urban mobility. The action plan is based on the suggestions made by the interested parties, by the citizens (both individually and through the associations that represent them) and by the European institutions and bodies⁴. The Commission points out that although urban mobility is managed by local authorities, the decisions taken in this regard are not totally autonomous, but chosen taking into account the European legal framework. The Commission identifies six themes: 1) Promoting

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/topics/single-market/services-general-interest_en

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/IT/TXT/?uri=legisum%3Atr0027>

³ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee, and the Committee of the Regions (COM (2009) 490 final)

⁴ COM(2009) 490, pag. 3 (Italian version).

Integrated Policies; 2) Focusing on Citizens; 3) Greening Urban Transportation; 4) Strengthening Funding; 5) Sharing Experience and Knowledge; and 6) Optimising Urban Mobility.

The Communication discovers its roots in the 2007 Green Paper, adopted by the Commission and entitled "Towards a New Culture for Urban Mobility"⁵).

Also in 2009, Directive 2009/33/EC established the obligation for contracting authorities to assess the environmental impact of urban vehicles, when purchasing them.

1.2 The Urban Mobility Package

In 2013 Comission announced the Urban Mobility Package⁶ to support towns and cities for the developmnet of sustainable urban mobility plan (SUMP) to stimulate transition towards cleaner and more sustainable transport in urban areas. The European Commission's 2013 Communication No. 913, " Together towards competitive and resource-efficient urban mobility"⁷ reinforces its supporting measures "the Urban Mobility Package" in the areas of urban transport by: 1) Sharing experiences, show-casing best practices, and fostering cooperation; 2) Providing targeted financial support; 3) Focusing research and innovation on delivering solutions for urban mobility challenges; 4) Involving the Member States and enhancing international cooperation. The commision through the Communication No. 913 recommnd a conceret set of measures to be taken for creating the framwork conditions for local authorities to boost development and inplemntation of integeated and comperhensive startegies for a sucessful transition towards a more sustainable urban mobility and to ensure European urban areas develop along a more sustainable path.

1.3 The Health and Environment Pan-European Programme (THE PEP)

In the field of sustainable mobility, a key role is carried out by the Transport, Health and Environment Pan-European Programme (THE PEP), established by the UNECE (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe). This program was launched in 2009, and its action plan affects transportation and sustainable mobility. Among the actions launched by the Pan-European Program, the 2009 Amsterdam Declaration and the 2014 Paris Declaration are the main pillars of sustainable transport. In its preamble, the Amsterdam Declaration affirms that the historical roots of THE PEP include the 1997 Vienna Declaration on Transport and Environment and the 1999 London Charter on Transport, Environment and Health. The Amsterdam Declaration sets out 4 Priority Goals: To contribute to sustainable economic development and stimulate job creation through investment in environment- and health-friendly transport; to manage sustainable mobility and promote a more efficient transport system; to reduce emissions of transport-

⁵ Green Paper Towards a new culture for urban mobility (COM(2007) 551 final)

⁶ https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/clean-transport-urban-transport/urban-mobility/urban-mobility-package_e

⁷ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:82155e82-67ca-11e3-a7e4-01aa75ed71a1.0011.02/DOC_3&format=PDF

related greenhouse gases, air pollutants and noise; to promote policies and actions conducive to healthy and safe modes of transport.

Contextually, the Declaration sets out a Work Plan (2014-2019) with five priority goals prescribed in the Paris Declaration "City in Motion – People First!"⁸:

- Priority Goal 1: to contribute to sustainable economic development and stimulate job creation through investment in environment- and healthfriendly transport
- Priority Goal 2: to manage sustainable mobility and promote a more efficient transport system
- Priority Goal 3: to reduce emissions of transport-related greenhouse gases, air pollution and noise
- Priority Goal 4: to promote policies and actions conducive to healthy and safe modes of transport;
- Priority Goal 5: to integrate transport, health and environmental objectives into urban and spatial planning policies

1.4 The 2014 Paris Declaration ("City in motion: People first")

As stated in its Introduction, the title of the Declaration "(...) Underlines the importance of placing citizens at the centre of decisions on transport and mobility: the emphasis is on people-centred policies designed to make safe, healthy and green transport choices accessible and affordable to all".

The Paris Declaration adds a fifth goal to those already launched in 2009: "To integrate transport, health and environmental objectives into urban and spatial planning policies".

Chapter III establishes as THE PEP vision a "Green and healthy mobility and transport for sustainable livelihoods for all", affirming the joint decision to intensify their work in the framework of THE PEP "to achieve safe, efficient, accessible, affordable, inclusive, green and healthy mobility and transport" and to strengthen the objectives outlined. Chapter IV outlines the mechanisms to concretely achieve the targets set, within the Work Plan 2014-2020; these include: the implementation of NTHEAPs (National Transportation, Health and Environment Action Plans), THE PEP Relay Race (Relays), and THE PEP Partnerships. Chapter V defines the institutional framework, while Chapter VI addresses resources; among the items, THE PEP is commits to allocate the finances necessary to implement the Work Plan.

1.5 The European Green Deal

The European Commission's 2019 Communication No. 640, "The European Green Deal," reiterates the key role played by the EU in relation to current and future challenges concerning the climate change.

The Communication outlines a set of goals, starting from paragraph 2; among them, it is establishing a transformation of the economy with the aim of achieving climate neutrality within 2050.

In Section 2.1.2, "Supplying clean, affordable and secure energy," the Commission states the importance of implementing further decarbonization of the energy system; in this context, it emphasizes the importance of realizing smart infrastructure. Section 2.1.3, "Mobilizing industry for a clean and circular

⁸ https://unece.org/DAM/thepep/Publications/2015_and_pdf_Signs_and_signals/Paris_Declaration_in_English_Final.pdf

economy," focuses on the key role of industry in achieving climate neutrality. The last point emphasizes how the use of digital technologies is essential in order to achieve sustainability goals.

Section 2.1.4, "Building and renovating in an energy and resource efficient way," focuses on building renovation in order to pursue both energy efficiency and energy affordability.

Section 2.1.5, "Accelerating the shift to sustainable and smart mobility," hinges on transportation.

Assuming that transport is responsible for a quarter of the EU's greenhouse gas emissions, the Commission states the need to reduce transport emissions by 90% within 2050.

To achieve this, the Commission points out the importance to offer users "more affordable, accessible, healthier and cleaner alternatives" to their transportation habits. With this regard, the Commission highlights the key role of multimodal transportation along with digitization.

Furthermore, the Communication reaffirms the importance of increasing the production and deployment of sustainable alternative fuels for the transportation sector. Finally, it set the target to drastically reduce transport pollution, especially in cities; tools to achieve this goal include improving public transportation.

Section 2.1.6 focuses on the design of "a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system", while section 2.1.7 - on the preservation and restoration of ecosystems and biodiversity. In conclusion, in section 2.1.8, the Commission sets the goal of "a zero pollution ambition for a toxic-free environment".

Section 2.2 refers to EU policies, establishing the integration of sustainability into each of them.

The Commission outlines a set of goals in order to achieve this goal. First, "Pursuing green finance and investment and ensuring a just transition" (point 2.2.1); in this sense, the Commission states that 30% of the Invest EU Fund will be allocated to the fight against climate change. Furthermore, "projects will be subject to sustainability proofing to screen the contribution that they make to climate, environmental and social objectives". The Commission clarifies that a special focus will be given to regions and sectors which will be most affected by the transition, due to their dependence on fossil fuels or carbon-intensive processes. In this respect, it is stated "the need for a socially just transition must also be reflected in policies at EU and national level", which "includes investment to provide affordable solutions to those affected by carbon pricing policies, for example through public transport, as well as measures to address energy poverty and promote re-skilling".

Section 2.2.2 ("Greening national budgets and sending the right price signals") hinges on the decisive role of national budgets in the transition.

Finally, the sections 2.2.3 to 2.2.5 deal with essential factors such as the development of research and innovation, education and training and the relevance of "A green oath: 'do no harm'".

Section 3 establishes the role of the European Union as a global leader, in response to climate change; in addition, section 4 outlines the achievement of a "European Climate Pact".

1.6 Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy – putting European transport on track for the future

The European Commission's 2019 Communication No.640 refers to the objectives set out in the new European Green Deal⁹, specifying their scope with reference to the transport sector.

Paragraph 1 starts with an outline of the European transport vision: the free movement of people and goods is a fundamental freedom of the EU and its single market; today, the most relevant challenge in the field of transport is the emissions reduction and the implementation of sustainability.

Paragraph 9 states the importance of changing the current people's mindset - leading to (small) changes which can involve, in their entirety, a total transformation.

In order to accomplish this result, three core targets are identified:

- By 2030: at least 30 million zero-emission vehicles will be in operation on European roads; 100 European cities will be climate neutral; high-speed rail traffic will double; scheduled collective travel of under 500 km should be carbon neutral within the EU; automated mobility will be deployed on a large scale; zero-emission vessels will become ready for market.
- By 2035: zero-emission large aircraft will become ready for market.
- By 2050: nearly all cars, vans, buses as well as new heavy-duty vehicles will be zero emission; rail freight traffic will double; high-speed rail traffic will triple; the multimodal Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) equipped for sustainable and smart transport with high-speed connectivity will be operational for the comprehensive network.

2 TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE APPRAISALS METHODS AND EUROPEAN MOBILITY DECISION-MAKING PROCESS

The most prominent use of cost-benefit analysis (CBA) in the transport domain is investment appraisal for maximizing profit when applying public funds. In the EU, almost all member states have their national guidelines for evaluation of transport infrastructure projects to ensure that the most profitable project advances in planning. However, the in-place guidelines for transport project appraisal are based on national regulations and frameworks which contain a wide range of effects and individual values that varies across countries. In general, the assessment frameworks are in alignment with EU policies.

As from 2000, the EU cohesion policy requires a (CBA) for projects in order to qualify for funding from various sources (e.g. Structural Funds, Cohesion Funds and Instruments for Pre-Accession Assistance).

Article 40(e) of the Regulation 1083/2006 lays down the requirement to provide a CBA for major projects financed under the Operational Programmes for cohesion policy. The projects can only receive EU grants, if it is desirable from a socio-economic point of view. (EC DG Regional Policy,2008).

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/european-green-deal-communication_en.pdf

For the period 2021-2027, a more flexible and proportional approach is proposed, consistent with the approach to economic appraisal followed by the European Investment Bank (EIB) and other potential implementing partners (see below). The new approach will be presented in the Economic Appraisal Vademecum (EAV) that is being prepared for publication by DG REGIO in coordination with other Commission DGs and with the support of JASPERS. The EAV will complement, not replace, the Commission's 2014 CBA Guide and is meant to be a resource that can be used across different funds in the 2021-2027 financial perspective. Although CBA will remain the default appraisal tool for several Commission-funded initiatives, other tools are suggested in specific circumstances¹⁰.

In the last decades, many detailed reviews on appraisal methods for transport infrastructure projects are available. (Mackie et al. 2014, Odgaard et al., 2006, Nijkamp et al. 2003, Grant-Muller et al. 2001, Bristow and Nellthorp 2000). But the most comprehensive study on transport appraisal was performed by the HEATCO project¹¹ in 2005, to investigate the appraisal methods and values being used by 25 EU Member States in transport projects for proposing a Harmonised European Approaches for Transport Costing and project assessment. As part of HEATCO results it can be found that the CBA is a common appraisal tool in all 25 studied countries that complemented in 9 EU countries (Austria, Switzerland, Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia, Cyprus, Spain and UK) for road transport projects assessment. According to literature review, three appraisal techniques have been broadly used in academic studies and in practice that together with their strengths and limitations are discussed in following chapters.

2.1 Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA)

Cost benefit analysis (CBA) is the widely used tool for transport investments as an ex-ante method to evaluate the cost and benefits of transport (infrastructure) projects (Berechman, 2009, Morisugi & Hayashi 2000, Martnes & Di Ciommo 2017). This analysis usually consists of determining the Net benefits (i.e. the Transport User benefits + Wider economic impacts + Social impacts) and the Net cost (i.e. Construction cost + +operating cost + maintenance + users' costs – revenues). Benefits may depend both on the user's travel purpose and also on the time of the day. But there are no unique CBA methods. Examples for benefits are given in the table below.

¹⁰ https://europa.eu/investeu/system/files/2021-04/investeu_sustainability_proofing_guidance_en_0.pdf

¹¹ <https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/project/developing-harmonised-european-approaches-transport-costing-and-project-assessment>

BENEFIT	DISAGGREGATED BENEFIT	DESCRIPTION OF BENEFIT
Transport user benefit	Improved access	With new lines and more stations, journey between the origin (house/work, etc) and the rail station or between stations can be shortened.
	Reductions in crowding	Passengers experience a more pleasant journey as vehicles are less crowded.
	Improvements in interchange	More options to change methods of transport across the network.
	Reductions in waiting	Increase frequency, less time waiting for the train.
	Reductions in journey times	As a result of new lines/improvement of current lines journey times can be reduced.
	Benefits to road users	With better public transport options, less vehicles will be on the road. Remaining drivers encounter less traffic and traffic jams.
Wider economic impact	Increased labour mobility	Better public transport can affect individual incentives to work in other areas.
	Agglomeration benefits	New transport methods may benefit businesses and lead to further business interaction
	More revenues for transport authorities	Higher revenue creation for transport authorities if more people use the public transport. ROI of investing in public transport is higher as more people use it.
Social impacts	Reduction of car noise	Less cars on the road, so there will be less noise caused by cars.
	Reduction of carbon emissions	Less cars on the road could mean reduction in carbon emissions.
	Fewer traffic fatalities	Reduction of likelihood of injuries and loss of life caused by car accidents.

Source: MoTiV project¹²

CBA as the most common tool for economic evaluation of projects and investments has an advantage compared to the traditional accounting techniques and methods such as considering externalities and observed price distortions that appropriately reflect the market imperfections. CBA also has the disadvantage of extensive data requirements, necessity of quantifying and monetizing all impacts (Browne and Ryne 2011). Having said that, like other evaluation techniques, there are some strengths and limitation in applying CBA methods for public transport project appraisals highlighted in the EVALSED sourcebook ¹³ as follows:

Strengths

- enables us to express an opinion on the socio-economic convenience of a project;
- enables us to create rankings among projects;
- encourages the practice of identifying the economic benefits and costs, even if they are not immediately monetisable.

Limitations

- does not take redistributive effects into consideration (for these, one can use a multicriteria analysis);

¹² <https://motivproject.eu/>

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/publications/evaluations-guidance-documents/2013/evalsed-the-resource-for-the-evaluation-of-socio-economic-development-sourcebook-method-and-techniques

- does not consider the effect on the economic return of non-monetisable benefits or costs;
- sometimes uses discretionary criteria for the monetisation of the costs and benefits for which no market exists.

2.2 Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) or Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)

MCA is one of the methods developed on basis of the criticism of CBA (Thomopoulos et al., 2009). It is “capable of eliciting the trade-offs between objectives (e.g., transportation efficiency, improved equity, and reduced environmental externalities) in ways that enable decision makers to make rational and systematic choices regarding the preferred project” (Berechman, 2009, p. 306).

This method has evolved as a multi-objective decision making approach for situations in which a single-criterion approach is incapable of providing the required assessment framework due to usually conflicting criteria (Berechman, 2009; Thomopoulos et al., 2009). MCA aims to “to allow each decision-making environment to engender its own set of criteria, measure and score them, and then generate a system of relative weights specific to the given context.” (Berechman, 2009, p. 308) It needs to be clearly pointed out that “[p]articipation of the decision-makers in the process is a central part of the approach.” (Thomopoulos et al., 2009, p. 3). MCA differs from CBA in the following two main areas:

- MCA has no limits in the forms of criteria in the sense of that MCA allows also for “intangible” elements like for instance equity considerations; and
- MCA does not require the use of prices, MCA makes use of weights and scores (note that prices might be used though to derive these overall scores).

Strengths

- Openness to divergent values and opinions
- Support to a broad stakeholder participation
- Preferences revealed in a more direct and practical way
- Capability to tackle qualitative and intangible impacts
- Help to legitimize decision-makers' behaviour.

Limitations

- Subjectivity of generated weights
- Technical complexity (for instance the choice of parameters)
- Potentially time-consuming process
- Experts' reluctance to share their knowledge/power
- Information bias from certain stakeholder groups to strengthen their power.

2.3 Social Welfare Analysis

The social welfare functions (SWF) or social welfare analysis in the economy context which rely on the individuals' subjective well-being assessment that is concerned with distribution of individuals' utility. (Dolan and Tsuchiya 2011). In scientific literature, the SWF was argued by Dolan and Tsuchiya 2011 as a powerful tool to find the best balance between the competing objectives of efficiency and equality and valuations of individual benefit and cost based on people's preferences (Rabin 1993, Fehr and Schmitt 1999, Dolan and Tsuchiya 2011). The SWF methodology is also disputed by Adler et al. (2017) as a "tool for ethical deliberation, more specifically ethical deliberation that is consequentialist and welfarist". In practice, there are three types of SWF evaluation of public project which help decision makers to find out the extent to which a policy or project will change social welfare (increase or decrease). These evaluation methods are different in terms of aggregate net benefits.

- **Method1:** This method tries to integrate efficiency and equity values. For doing so, the appraisals of a policy or project incorporates social equity weights to Willingness to Pay (WTP) for different groups of individuals. This kind of evaluation is usually applied in academic studies by using the equity-weighted measures of net social benefit (NSB) for specific groups of people that can be widely used in public project appraisals.
- **Method2:** Projects are evaluated with an efficiency criterion such as unweighted NSB.
- **Method3:** This method assumes the importance of both efficiency and equity for the project evaluation but treats efficiency and equity separately. In this approach results are presented to the decision makers in two formats: a) the evaluated aggregate NSB of a public project b) a description of the distributional impacts

Limitation¹⁴

- The assessment is based on valuations of individual preferences and the evaluation is sensitive to distributional aspects such as income distribution. Thus, comparison and aggregation of the valuations in case of utilitarian SWF raise greater problems as the marginal utility of income varies across individuals.
- Social valuations of marginal income may vary according to the level of wellbeing of individuals in society.
- There is no ready technical basis for weighing the benefits and costs into an overall measure of social welfare. Assessment of welfare improvement derived from transport public projects requires a detailed classification of various stakeholders and a standard model to measure for instance the equity impact in a monetary sense.

¹⁴ <http://www.appliedeconomics.com.au/publications/public-economics/07-201803-social-welfare-and-economic-evaluation.htm>

3 THE MAJOR IMPACTS CONTRIBUTING IN TRANSPORT PROJECT APPRAISALS

3.1 Financial Impacts (Direct Impacts)

Financial impacts are predominantly incorporated in a CBA for transport system appraisal. All countries have a money value for construction cost, operating cost, maintenance, time saving, safety and users' costs -revenues. These impacts are evaluated according to market value or nationally agreed value.

- **Travel Time saving:**

There is a broad consensus on including travel time saving in transport project appraisal that are valued in a monetary sense. Current value of travel time definitions and methodologies for its assessment and subsequent recommendations focus on time and cost savings related to the personal "Travel Time Budget" (TTB), the constant amount of time one invests in daily mobility. In a nutshell, Value of Travel Time (VTT) is defined as the cost of time spent on transport. Accordingly, VTT is defined as the maximum amount of money that one is willing to pay to save a minute of travel time.

Time savings as a key objective of transport projects appraisal are distinguished between work and non-work (leisure) travel time that are given different monetary valuation. Usually in the European countries work travel time is given a higher value implying higher efficiency and productivity for the time saved. For the non-work travel time saving there is no unique approach at the EU level for measuring the value of time save. However, people's willingness to pay (WTP) or willingness to accept (WTA) are the most applied approaches for valuation of time saved in non-work travel time.

Work or leisure travel time are often discussed differently in VTT literature: in the former case, VTT is a cost to employers for the time spent on travel by employees, while in the latter it is a cost for personal (unpaid) time spent on travel. The association of value of time to cost is in line with the idea that "time is money".

As reported by HEATCO project, majority of EU countries in north and west regions have segregated values for passengers' work and non-work travel time saving which are estimated based on either national values or techniques proposed in national guidelines by local governments. In these countries, the most dominant methods for valuation of work travel time are cost saving, Hensher formula and WTP using national salary rate; while the non-work travel time is valued based on different methods accepted by national governments such as percentage of wage rate, and WTP for adhering in transport projects appraisal. Exploring the valuation of travel time also reveals that some EU countries such as Czech Republic, Slovakia, Spain, Belgium, and Hungary apply average travel time value in the project appraisal instead of segregating the work and non-work travel time. The most common methods taken by EU countries for disaggregating work and non-work travel time saving values are based on transport mode, trip purpose, travel distance, time of day, urban/interurban, passenger/driver and level of income which are affecting value of time. For instance, in the case of France the value of travel time saving varies

according to travel distance, mode of transport and urban and inter-urban trips, while in the Netherlands the value of travel time is differentiated by income group and being passenger or driver.

To sum up, as widely seen in the literature and reports on valuation of travel time, travel time saving values are varying across the EU member states as they are highly dependent on national wage rate. However, less known is instead what value of travel time means for end users, in relation to their needs, expectations, and lifestyles.

- **Safety:**

Safety along with travel time saving is the major contributor adhered in CBA for transport project appraisal, and almost in all EU countries accidents and materials, damaged by accidents, are given monetary values in European investment appraisals for cost per fatality according to national values or European common monetary values. The preferred method as stated in CBA guideline¹⁵ for the evaluation of financial cost of accidents saving is employing preferred or revealed preference techniques based on concepts of WTP/ WTA using either survey of individuals (insurance) or politicians (e.g., the values implicit in authorities decision making that affect safety (Bristow and Nellthorp, 2000), or hedonic wage method. In regard to safety evaluation and in particular accidents saving, three types of costs have a pivotal role in appraisals: **Direct Cost** arisen from damage to vehicle, property, emergency services, medical treatment. **Cost to the economy** in terms of lost production when a person is killed or injured and **cost to society** in terms the prevented immaterial damage from death and injury (e.g., pain, grief, and suffering). According to the HEATCO project, all EU member states in north and west include these three factors in the transport framework appraisal. However, there are some exceptions such as Italy and Portugal that do not include direct cost arisen from damage to vehicle in safety appraisal; and countries such as Latvia, Spain and Slovenia which cost to society is not part of CBA in their national safety evaluation framework.

- **Vehicle operating costs**

Vehicle Operating Costs (VOCs) are defined as the costs accepted by owners of road vehicles to operate them, including fuel consumption, repair and maintenance costs, insurance, administration, etc. It is worth mentioning that VOCs are correlated with type of vehicle and average travel speed, but are also characteristics of roads such as design standards and surface conditions¹⁶

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/inea/sites/default/files/cba_guide_cohesion_policy.pdf

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/inea/sites/default/files/cba_guide_cohesion_policy.pdf

3.2 Environmental Impacts

Environment impacts in transport infrastructure projects are assessed based on three elements: noise, air pollution and climate change in terms of effects on global warming and ozone depletion.

According to HEATCO project, Noise is an impact where there is consensus that it should be included in appraisal, but no consensus as to how. Majority of EU countries use CBA and the remaining countries using other methods such MCA or descriptive analysis for translation of noise impacts considering the level of annoyance and health related cost to money values. The hedonic pricing is a commonly used technique among the majority of EU countries pricing. However, there are some exceptions where countries substitute the hedonic pricing with stated preference or contingent valuation analysis.

Road transport is a major source of air pollution (local, regional and global) that harms human health and the environment due to a range of pollutants including nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and particulate matter (PM) which are emitted from vehicles¹⁷. Albeit the EU has set limit values for the maximum amount of air pollution citizens should be exposed to in urban areas but the levels of NO₂ and PM are still above these limits.

Regarding the impact of air pollution there is general consensus that it should be included in a CBA for transport infrastructure project appraisals with a money value consisting of values for the following elements:

- Nitrogen oxides (NO_x)
- Particulate matter (PM)
- Sulphur dioxide (SO₂)
- Volatile organic compounds (VOC)
- Carbon monoxide (CO)

Among three monetising methods for the evaluation of the air pollution: impact pathway approach, other damage cost approach and avoidance costs (cost of avoiding emission)¹⁸, the impact pathway approach is broadly used by EU member states to calculate the impact as a cost.

According to the literature, for climate change there is no consensus on whether or not it should be incorporated in a cost-benefit analysis. However, some countries such as Austria, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Netherlands, Sweden, Switzerland, Czech Republic and Italy already admitted the inclusion of climate effects in a cost-benefit analysis.

As can be seen in publicly available documents, there are clear differences across EU member states on dealing with climate change impacts that cause no concrete agreement on a common approach for assessing monetary values.

¹⁷ <https://www.transportenvironment.org/what-we-do/air-quality-and-transport/road-vehicles-and-air-quality>

¹⁸ https://trimis.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/project/documents/20130122_113558_74349_hd1final.pdf

4 UTILIZED TRANSPORT APPRAISAL METHODS IN THE EU MEMBER STATES:

4.1 National Regulation on Transport Projects Assessment

ITALY

Within the Italian framework of infrastructural planning, it is possible to identify two fundamental pillars: the General Transport and Logistics Plan ("Piano Generale dei Trasporti e della Logistica", PGTL) and the Multiyear Planning Document ("Documento Pluriennale di Pianificazione", DPP)¹⁹.

The PGTL establishes the strategic objectives of the national transport system and outlines scenarios concerning the evolution of the national mobility system, which is based on national and international transport demand and supply forecasts.

Furthermore, the DPP constitutes the unitary instrument of triennial programming of the resources for public investments. The DPP hinges on three sections:

- analysis concerning the infrastructural needs;
- results of ex-ante evaluations and identification of the priority classes of intervention;
- criteria for ex-post evaluations of the identified interventions and summary of the results of ex-post evaluations already carried out.

The Guidelines for the Evaluation of Investments in Public Works (published by the Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport) highlight that within this framework the legislative decree no. 152/2006, concerning the "Environmental Impact Assessment", have an essential importance. Moreover, the Guidelines point out that the new Procurement Code ("Codice degli Appalti") has modified the levels of in-depth design by eliminating the preliminary project and by introducing the feasibility project with the aim to identify, among several solutions, the one which presents the best relationship between costs and benefits for the community, in relation to the specific needs to be met and services to be provided. The feasibility project includes the analysis both of financial sustainability and of economic and social convenience.

With reference to the Italian transportation planning, one of the key sources is the General Plan for Transport and Logistics ("Piano Generale dei Trasporti e della Logistica") as mentioned in the Presidential Decree of 14 March 2001 (and as updated by Legislative Decree 18 April 2016, no. 50).

The Guidelines anchor the ex-ante evaluation of projects to four phases:

- the analysis of the current demand and supply scenario
- identification of future scenarios of analysis (e.g. trend scenario of reference, high growth scenario, etc.)
- demand forecasting in such scenarios

¹⁹ Linee Guida per la Valutazione degli Investimenti in Opere Pubbliche, Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti, p. 1, see https://www.mit.gov.it/sites/default/files/media/notizia/2017/07/Linee%20Guida%20Val%20OO%20PP_01%2006%202017.pdf

- estimation of the functioning of the demand-supply system (e.g. saturation level of infrastructures) and of the related impacts on the external environment (e.g. pollutant emissions).

In addition, feasibility analyses are subjected to a differentiated analysis regime, based on the specific category of the work (see DPCM August 3, 2012, Annex I, point 2.5). Specifically:

a) With reference to capital renewal works (e.g. recovery and renovation) and new projects both with investments lower than 10 million euros and without tariff revenues. The evaluation techniques adopted are demand analysis and cost-effectiveness analysis.

b) Instead, with reference both to projects involving investments higher than 10 million euros and without tariff income and to projects of any size (except for capital renewal interventions), for which a service charge is envisaged. The assessment techniques applied are demand analysis; financial analysis; cost-benefit analysis; risk and sensitivity analysis.

Among the strategic objectives listed and common to all transport sectors, it is possible to notice:

- i. Sustainable mobility, namely how much the work contributes to reduce environmental pollution related to the movement of people and goods;
- ii. Accessibility to European transport networks, namely how much the work contributes to improving the accessibility of territories and populations towards Europe.

Furthermore, among the objectives is reported the urban, architectural and landscape quality, which is defined as 'how much the project contributes to improve the context in which it is located in terms of urban, architectural and landscape quality, even if it acts directly or indirectly on an existing infrastructure'.

SPAIN

In its Introduction, *the Guide on Economic Evaluation of Transport Project* ("Evaluación socioeconómica y financiera de proyectos de transporte"²⁰) states that the main objective of the economic appraisal of a transport project is to identify and quantify the project contribution to social welfare.

Furthermore, it affirms to start from the idea that public investment in transport infrastructure and services should be assessed using cost-benefit analysis (CBA).

The Guide establishes that each project has to be evaluated by considering the expected benefits in terms of increasing social welfare: the expected benefits have to overcome the costs allocated for its implementation. Such an assessment has to be carried out both before, during and after the implementation of the project. In the first phase, the assessment will allow to decide whether to carry out (or not) the project. In the following stages, the evaluation enables to understand if it is necessary to provide modifications or to acquire additional information which may consent to improve the design of future projects.

²⁰ <http://www.evaluaciondeproyectos.es/EnWeb/index.html>

Although the Guide states that the evaluation of a transportation project helps make decisions about the project by comparing the benefits and costs generated over time, at the same time it points out that in most transport projects, social benefits and costs are not limited to a mere accounting of revenues and costs. For example, when it is needed to quantify how much benefit a service of urban passenger transport generates to society, its benefits cannot be limited to gross income earned by those who supply the service, but must include the total valuation carried out by society, as measured by its total Willingness To Pay (WTP) including users and nonusers (for example, those who can drive their private vehicles at higher speeds).

Therefore, it is affirmed that the evaluation of a transportation project can be approached from two different perspectives: economic evaluation, considering the benefits and costs the project generates for society as a whole, or financial evaluation, just focusing on the revenues and costs generated by the project. Among the criteria considered for the evaluation and quantification of social costs and benefits, it is possible to notice those concerning the environmental externalities, in particular, noise, air pollution, landscape, soil contamination, water contamination, climate change (with particular reference to the emissions of greenhouse gases, such as CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O), vibrations.

AUSTRIA

With reference to years 2012-2020, the "Mobility for the Future" ("Mobilität der Zukunft") programme ²¹ carried out a key role.

Responsible for the development and implementation of this program was the BMVIT (Federal Ministry of Transport, Innovation and Technology), currently Federal Ministry of Austria, Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology; in such a role, it was supported by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG) and AustriaTech.

Regarding project evaluation, four basic criteria were established: relevance to the objectives; quality; qualification; economic potential. Additionally, the document emphasized that the program can also use instruments from the FFG's toolbox including provision of funds for dissertations, endowed professorships and programs designed to strengthen human resources in mobility and transport.

Within the current Austrian context, the "Austria's 2030 Mobility Master Plan" issued by the Federal Ministry Republic of Austria plays a key role ²².

The Plan aims to achieve a transition towards a mobility which is sustainable, climate-neutral, safe, resilient, gender-equal, social and economically viable, by 2040. The Plan explicitly mentions an alignment with European objectives.

²¹ Mobility of the Future, The Research, Technology and Innovation Program for Mobility 2012-2020, Federal Ministry for Transport, Innovation and Technology

²² Austria's 2030 Mobility Master Plan, The new climate action framework for the transport sector: sustainable – resilient – digital, Federal Ministry Republic of Austria, 2021.

The first goal set by the Plan relates to national climate neutrality: to reduce transport carbon emissions from 24 million tCO₂eq (2019 levels) to close to zero tCO₂eq. In such perspective, the Plan states that the strategic planning common to all modalities of transportation should be adapted in order to achieve this goal. Among the actions concerning this target, the following ones are of utmost importance:

- expansion of passenger transport, by rededicating traffic space for bicycle and foot traffic
- switch to zero-emission vehicle technologies.

In relation to the implementation of the targets set, the Plan affirms that reasearch, innovation and digitalisation should play a key role.

With regard to the legislative framework, the Plan states as a fundamental objective the realignment of the national transport regulation with the aim to achieve climate neutrality.

With such a perspective, the Plan sets three fundamental measures:

- implementing a climate check for existing legislation for the mobility sector
- creating room for experimentation to enable innovations, coordinated closely with nationwide activities in this area
- implementing the transport protocol of the Alpine Convention.

Examples of legal innovations planned to reach these goals include plans to reform the traffic code in order to make it more friendly to cyclists and pedestrians.

In relation to the economic framework, the Plan identifies the introduction of additional CO₂ pricing (both through tax measures and through the introduction of emission trading) as a key measure for achieving the environmental objectives set.

Moreover, the Plan points out that air pollution reduction meets the standards set at an international level and it will also reverberate on a consequential noise reduction.

A further fundamental role is attributed to the monitoring of the obtained results; in parallel, there emphasized the importance of transferring and sharing knowledge between the private, public and scientific sectors to develop new mobility services in synergy.

Among the social objectives, the document also identifies a set of benefits, such as access to mobility and traffic safety.

PORTUGAL

A transport strategy for Portugal article²³ pointed out that there is still no integrated transport policy and planning in Portugal. However, it stressed that common features are to be found to change a mobility paradigm from individual to collective transport.

²³ A transport strategy for Portugal, N.M. Gomes Rocha, p. 3, see <https://www.witpress.com/Secure/elibrary/papers/UT10/UT10001FU1.pdf>

Another common strategy concerned is renewable energy with the aim to increase efficiency and reduce environmental impact.

BELGIUM

As stated in the document *Federal Authority's vision of mobility in Belgium* "Vision de la Mobilité en Belgique de l'Autorité Fédérale" of 2017²⁴, the Belgium framework is based on a vision of mobility such as sustainable, intermodal, multimodal and digital.

Regarding the salient elements concerning mobility, the document reports the following objectives:

- reducing the transport environmental impact
- reducing the cost of congestion
- making transport more efficient, sustainable and safe
- providing an innovative response to congestion issues
- promoting the progressive implementation of smart vehicles.

Among the strategic orientations established by the Federal Authority, it is possible to find the promotion of multimodality and inter-modality, the orientation of supply and demand, and the integration of mobility with other policies (e.g.: environmental, urban planning, energy and social policy, taxation and public health).

In particular, two main challenges are identified: improving road safety and reducing traffic problems and establishing a National Intermodal Transportation Plan ("Plan de Transport National Intermodal").

FRANCE

France is the European Country with the highest public investment, accounting for 15% of total investment. Mainly, this investment concerns key sectors such as transport, energy and health.²⁵

In 2012, a map of investment programs and projects was implemented, the mapping concerned all the projects with more than 50 million euros and receiving more than 20% public funding (coming from state or local authorities); the number of projects concerning the transport sector was 181.

Furthermore, the final report of the mapping showed that Cost-benefit assessment has been implemented in a systematic way only with reference to projects concerning the transport sector.

Secondly, the Finance Law for 2012-2017 in its Article 17 stated that civil investment projects financed by the State, public establishments, public health facilities or health cooperation organizations are subject to a preliminary cost-benefit assessment. Finally, significant projects, for which the total cost of the project and the share of funding provided by the public bodies exceeds the thresholds set by decree must first be subjected to an independent counter evaluation.

²⁴ Vision de la Mobilité en Belgique de l'Autorité Fédérale, Arthur D. Little, Service Public Fédéral Mobilité et Transports, Bruxelles 3 Juillet 2017, see https://mobilit.belgium.be/sites/default/files/resources/files/adl_vision_federale_de_la_mobilite_synthese.pdf

²⁵ Cost-Benefit Assessment of Public Investments in France: The Use of Counter-Experts, Luc Baumstark, Roger Guesnerie, Jincheng Ni, Jean-Paul Ourliac, 2020, p. 2, see https://www.strategie.gouv.fr/sites/strategie.gouv.fr/files/atoms/files/bca_2000030_fn_public.pdf

Furthermore, regarding major projects, in which the financing implemented by the State and its public institutions exceeds 100 million euros, independent counter-experts have to evaluate the previous socio-economic assessment carried out by the project promoter.

As of December 2019, 68 projects were analysed, of which 16 related to infrastructure projects (with a median cost of 1907 M€). Regarding the socio-economic assessment, a reference source is the 2017 Guide.

Finally, the article emphasizes that socio-economic evaluation has to take into account the objectives set from an environmental perspective, too. As reported in the document "The Value for Climate Action" of 2019, France's objective is to achieve the goal of climate neutrality, or net zero GHG emissions ("Net-Zero"), inscribed in the 2015 Paris Agreement and in the 2017 Climate Plan.

NORDIC COUNTRIES (Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden) ²⁶

With regard to the economic methods applied, the Report "Appraisal Methods in the Nordic Countries" highlights that aside from Finland, the other countries make use of Net Present Value (NPV), as the primary value criteria. In Sweden NPV is used in a moderated form as it is set in relation to the total costs. This provides an indication of the net benefits per invested Swedish krona (SEK). In Norway NPV is only employed as one criterion value among many, as the value criteria can serve various purposes. NPV is then most often used for assessing the projects profitability, while the cost-benefit ratio is normally used to rank projects. First-year benefit can be used to assess the timing for a given project, while the purpose behind the Internal Rate of Return (IRR) will normally be to assess the project as a private investment.

In relation to Finland, the Report specifies that the Net benefit cost ratio (NBCR) is computed as the ratio of the NPV and the present value of investment costs.

The Report also refers to external costs and their evaluation, where the external costs are defined as costs imposed on others but not paid for. This is the case for unintended side effects such as environmental pollution. In that case the welfare of other people may be affected without the one responsible taking these costs into account in a decision-making process. External costs are the opposite of internal costs which have an influence on the decision to perform the activity or not.

In particular, the external costs taken into consideration are accident, noise, local and global air pollution.

BULGARIA

According to the CBA Guidelines for Transport Sector²⁷ in Bulgaria, the project options are usually composed of two different phases: the first phase (named as "pre-feasibility"), consisting of reducing a

²⁶ Appraisal Methods in the Nordic Countries, Transport Infrastructure Assessment, Report 3 2007, Stéphanie Vincent Lyk-Jensen, Danish Transport Research Institute, see <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.507.4446&rep=rep1&type=pdf>.

²⁷ https://www.rail-infra.bg/upload/529/CBA_Guidelines_Transport_BG_finalDec08.pdf

larger number of theoretically possible alternatives to a limited number of worthwhile assessing options, and a second phase (denominated as “feasibility”), consisting of assessing in more detail the technical, economical, financial and environmental feasibility of the shortlisted options in view of: (i) Selecting the optimal option; (ii) Checking if the selected option is worthwhile financing.

In the first phase, the shortlisting of the options could be done through a multi-criteria analysis. The Guidelines list some criteria (specifying that additional criteria could also be applied), such as: objectives; demand; environment (e.g.: pollution; loss of nature; etc); economic return; opportunities; requirements. As evaluative methods, the Guide suggests that the appraisal of the options under each indicator could be for instance carried out with the help of a five-point scale .

With regard to the second phase, it is recommended that the CBA (in particular the economic rate of return) is normally used if not as the sole in any case as one of the main selection criteria. At the same time, it is specified that the CBA can not be applied in cases where a particularly special nature of the project makes such criterion inadequate.

ESTONIA

The Report of the International Monetary Fund concerning the Republic of Estonia²⁸ points out that in Estonia there provided a double track of project evaluation; as a rule, a complete technical, economic and financial analysis is applied to major projects. However, there is no standard methodology that is applied by all Ministries.

Furthermore, the Report emphasizes that such complete assessments apply both to European projects and, as a rule, to large national projects. There are, however, different appraisal procedures for individual ministries and subsectors. In addition, the Report clarifies that The National Audit Office (NAO) is monitoring the appraisals for the largest projects, and if it has reservations about their integrity, it even conducts audits at the appraisal stage. The results of the appraisals of EU projects are published at the bidding stage, while the results for nationally funded projects are not published.

Among the required elements provided for the appraisal of projects under the cohesion policy, it is possible to find the following: definition of objectives; identification of the project; technical analysis and environmental sustainability; financial analysis; economic analysis; and risk assessment.

Instead, in relation to the criteria required for nationally funded projects, the following can be noticed: to be linked to the relevant sectoral development plan; to have an impact on other fields/areas; to produce an increase both in the quality and accessibility of public services; to be sustainable and effective.

Specifically, with reference to “large projects”, which are usually major infrastructure projects, it is possible to distinguish five required phases:

- Phase one: project idea note;

²⁸ Republic of Estonia, Technical Assistance Report – Public Investment Management Assessment, International Monetary Fund, June 2019, IMF Country Report No. 19/152.

- Phase two: pre-feasibility;
- Phase three: feasibility;
- Phase four: implementation preparation;
- Phase five: budget application.

In particular, among the sub-stages in which the third phase is divided, we can find the economic analysis – comprehensive of CBA and economic impact, also required for medium-size projects.

SLOVAKIA

In order to strengthen the efficiency of public spending, since 2016 the Slovak government established a Public Investment Management Assessment (PIMA)²⁹ to improve the management of public resources.

The PIMA assessment is divided into three phases: planning, allocation, and implementation. In particular, it is possible to observe that design of all PIM institutions in implementation phase is very strong.

With particular reference to project appraisal in the planning phase, the institutional framework requires that major projects be evaluated on a standard methodology, but results not published.

In relation to the Investment Planning, the Report highlights how the Country lacks a unified national strategy. Indeed, it is only possible to detect sectoral strategies with varying quality due to a lack of common methodology to produce them. Therefore, the process of selecting specific infrastructure programs and projects is not always based on demonstrating their contribution to meeting the objectives pursued in the strategies or on defined economic and social criteria.

With particular reference to the transport sector, the Slovak “Strategic Transport Development Plan” and the “Environmental Strategy” do not delineate a financial dimension nor a Cost-Benefit Analysis in relation to selected priority measures. The Report points out how these two strategies identify high-level strategic objectives and measures to be undertaken till 2030, but lack a monitoring matrix which would enable monitoring their implementation. There is currently no comprehensive list of public investment projects financed from domestic or other sources.

In relation to transport sector, the “Strategic Transport Development Plan” includes among its strategic objectives the regular monitoring of noise and air quality and implementation of measures reducing negative environmental transport impacts. In relation to this key-goal, the document fixes three guide lines to ensure preparation and conditions for systematic and conceptual transport development in Slovakia:

- improve the safety, efficiency and sustainability of transport operations by enhancing new technologies
- systematically reduce negative socio-economic and environmental impacts by transport

²⁹ SLOVAK REPUBLIC TECHNICAL ASSISTANCE REPORT—PUBLIC INVESTMENT MANAGEMENT ASSESSMENT, International Monetary Fund, IMF Country Report No. 19/330, October 2016, IMF Country Report No. 19/330, see <https://www.imf.org/content/dam/IGEUR/Documents/Slovak%20Republic%20PIMA.pdf>

- ensure that public and non-motorised transport is an attractive social benefit and becomes the natural choice in urban agglomerations.

GREECE

Fundamental pillar in the Greece context is the National Transport Model (NTM) ³⁰. NTM has a key function in relation to the strategic planning activities of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport. Furthermore, this model is the basis to identify and develop strategies to alleviate the shortcomings of the current transport system and to develop the future transport system in a converging direction of meeting future demand and promoting the economic and social development of the country without compromising its sustainability.

The model will produce quantitative results allowing determining impacts of the strategy alternatives and of the measures on traffic conditions, as well as social and environmental impacts. In this perspective, four key-objectives are identified:

- Identification of shortcomings / bottlenecks / needs for improvement
- Development of strategy alternatives
- Development of policies, investment strategies, projects and measures
- Assessment of the impacts of the different alternatives and selection of the most appropriate option.

As a rule, the Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) is used by applying quantitative and qualitative criteria. The report underlines that the relevant criteria used for the MCA relate directly to the so-called "High Level Objectives" (i.e., those of which major goals are connected to the sectorial plan of a country) -n the case for transport, with the dimension of its national development strategy. In this respect, five goals are enucleated:

- Primarily, to promote economic growth and efficiency. For this purpose, a Cost-Benefit Analysis is applied, which uses estimated costs and alignments for the relevant infrastructure proposals;
- To increase regional and international connectivity;
- To ensure environmental sustainability; in particular, the impact of the intervention on greenhouse gas emissions has been used as the sole indicator for environmental sustainability, as this provides also an indication of overall fuel consumption in the network;
- To increase personal accessibility and social inclusion;
- To ensure safety and security.

With specific reference to the development phases of transportation infrastructure, Law No. 4412/2016 outlines the development stages; specifically, the law refers to two types of projects: Road and rail projects; Marine/ Harbour Engineering Projects. It is possible to identify five phases: i) Planning and

³⁰ National Transport Plan for Greece, Final Transport Plan Report, June 2019, p. 21, see http://www.nationaltransportplan.gr/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Final_NTPG_en_20190624.pdf

Preparation of the Public Contract File; ii) Conceptual Design; iii) Preliminary Design; iv) Detailed Design; v) Implementation Design.

Nonetheless, the Report highlights that the law does not specify the need for identifying and comparing alternatives nor mentions anything on CBA, financial analysis, risk analysis, climate change or environmental impact assessment at preliminary stage. This has led to weaknesses and subsequent delays in the preparation of projects for external grant funding or financing.

GERMANY

In Germany, the Cost-Benefit Analysis is a cornerstone in the evaluation of projects. It is complemented by non-monetary Spatial Impact Assessment (SIA) and Environmental Risk Assessment (EIA) with Habitats Directive Assessment (HDA).³¹

With reference to the appraisal implemented in the framework of BVWP ("Bundesverkehrswegeplan", i.e. Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan), it is possible to distinguish nine different stages:

1. Registration of project applications by stakeholders (Federal government, Federal states, Deutsche Bahn AG, Federal Waterways and Shipping Administration, Interest groups)
2. Development of data basis and appraisal methodology
3. Development of background scenarios
4. Forecast of traffic demand and assignment to networks
5. Assessment of project impacts (CBA and complementary non-monetary)
6. Classification of projects and development of priority ranking
7. Revision after consultation with federal states and other stakeholders
8. Cabinet decision and presentation to parliament by Federal Government
9. Parliamentary decision by Bundesrat and Bundestag on infrastructure development acts.

Among the non-economic criteria considered, of note are the Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA) and Habitats Directive Assessment (HDA).

NETHERLANDS

In the Netherlands framework, several criteria are used to evaluate transport projects; the context of the time, noting how the criteria could vary on the basis of the project classification as outlined by Gwilliam and Nash (1992)³²

For instance, with reference to formal road investment, it was possible to find economic criteria consisting of Cost-Benefit Analysis, with an impact of 35% in the evaluation³³.

³¹ Gühnemann, A (2013) International Comparison of Transport Appraisal Practice - Annex 2 Germany Country Report. Research Report., University of Leeds, p. 4. See <https://eprints.whiterose.ac.uk/76699/1/analysis.10>

³² <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02688867.1992.9726873>

³³ K M Gwilliam & M J P F Gommers (1992) Transport project appraisal in the Netherlands, Project Appraisal, p. 7, see <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/02688867.1992.9726873>

Furthermore, additional non-economic criteria are taken into consideration, such as safety; environment; land use planning; transit role.

The article observes that for all elements except land-use planning and the transit role, the assessment is in cardinal form. It is worth noting that there are some special problems that arise in combining cardinal and ordinal rankings in a multi-criteria analysis (MCA), which have caused a great deal of emphasis to be placed on the choice of the form of MCA to be employed. Specifically, the "land use planning" and "transit role" criteria impact 5% and 15%, respectively.

Instead, in relation to inland waterways, it is applied a Multi-Criteria approach, where a part of it is a simple cost-benefit analysis, which generates some of the information used in the MCA.

With reference to rail projects, an information profile is necessary showing consistency of the project with the national transport plan, as well as demonstrating that alternative solutions have been considered, evidence of the traffic demands on which the proposal is based, and so on.

However, it is possible to observe that the checklist does not include any formal appraisal on either a financial or a cost-benefit basis, though a research project by the Netherlands Economic Institute is concerned with the establishment of an appraisal system for public transport projects of a comparable kind to that applied to major road schemes.

In the current context, transparency constitutes a pillar in the project planning in each design stage. For example, a standard component of every MIRT [Multi-Year Programme for Infrastructure, Spatial Planning, and Transport] phase involves mapping the impact and cost of solutions based on criteria that have been set down in concert (assessment framework).

The path which leads to the acceptance of the realization of a project by the MIRT opens with an exploratory phase (which starts with an "Initial Decision"), consisting of the drafting of a document in which tasks and strategies will be set. Attention is paid to sustainability, energy neutrality, and climate adaptation.

The screening of the best solutions is of paramount importance, with reference to both the best solutions and the legal and financial procedures to be preferred.

IRELAND

The Report "Common Appraisal Framework for Transport Projects and Programmes" outlines the project appraisal related to Irish transport projects ³⁴.

The document identifies different types of evaluation, on the basis of the project cost: for minor projects, with an estimated cost less than 0.5 million euros (e.g.: minor refurbishment works), a simple assessment, consisting of a less detailed evaluation is required. Instead, for projects costing between 0.5 and 5 million

³⁴ Common Appraisal Framework for Transport Projects and Programmes, Department of Transport, March 2016 (Updated October 2020).

euros, a single appraisal is required incorporating elements of a preliminary and detailed appraisal at a minimum.

Furthermore, projects between 5 million and 20 million euros should be subject to preliminary and detailed appraisal which includes at least a Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA). Moreover, projects with life time costs of over 20 million euros should have a Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) carried out.

In relation to current expenditure (with an annual spend of at least 5 million euros), a Detailed Economic Appraisal, i.e. Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) or Cost Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) is required.

Lastly, Capital Grant Schemes with an annual value in excess of 30 million euros and of 5 years or more duration are to be subject to prior and mid-term evaluation at the beginning and mid-point of each 5 year cycle or as may be agreed with the Department of Public Expenditure and Reform.

For each project, a Sanctioning Authority of reference is provided, in particular, with regard to projects costing more than 100 million euros, the Government will be the Sanctioning Authority. However, the Government could fulfil this role also for project with less value.

4.1.1 COMPARISON AMONG STUDIED COUNTRIES – AREAS OF CONVERGENCE AND POINTS OF DIVERGENCE

With regard to the Countries analysed, an initial point of convergence could be detected in relation to the identification of different project levels, based on the cost of the project: with reference to this classification, it is possible to observe a differentiated system of analysis and evaluation.

Regarding this last aspect, it is possible to identify the first point of divergence at national level: the methodology applied differs from country to country. For instance: Ireland requires a "simple assessment" for minor projects (specifically, with a value between 0.5 and 5 million euros), while it requires a detailed analysis (including at least a Multi-Criteria Analysis) for projects with a cost between 5 and 20 million euros.

However, in Estonia a detailed analysis (comprehensive of four phases) is required only for projects defined as "large"; and to be classified as such, a project has to meet a series of criteria (see above).

Therefore, it is possible to identify points of divergence both on the basis of the criteria applied to classify the various projects (between minor and major) and on the basis of the methodologies required to analyze them. Instead, a further point of convergence is to be detected in relation to environmental impact: all the national regulations examined foresee the implementation of analyses on this aspect.

In regard to a broad application of CBA, in particular in the context of EU TEN-T multimodal transport planning, the following objectives are usually pursued: reduction of congestion within a network, link or node by resolving capacity constraints; improvement of the capacity and/or performance of a network, link or node by increasing travel speeds and by reducing operating costs and accidents; improvement of the reliability and safety of a network, minimisation of GHG emissions, pollution and limitation of the environmental impact (important examples are projects supporting the shift from individual, i.e. cars, to

collective transport); adjustment to EU standards and completion of missing links or poorly linked networks: transport networks have often been created on a national and/or regional basis, which may no longer meet the transport requirements of the single market (this is mainly the case with railways); improvement of accessibility in peripheral areas or regions.

In particular, among the factors affecting the economic analysis, it is possible to detect the following: travel time savings; vehicle operating costs savings; operating costs of carriers; accidents savings; variation in noise emissions; variation in air pollution; variation in GHG emissions while the human well-being measures (values) in case of an individual's real or idealised preferences are ignored or have less been paid attention.

5 VALUES TO BE CONSIDERED FOR MULTI-MODAL TRANSPORT APPRAISAL (BEYOND THE TRADITIONAL SPEED-TIME-PRICE PARADIGM)

5.1 Equity: Accessibility and Social Inclusion

Transport project appraisals are still mostly based on maximizing benefit of transport infrastructure and services while neglecting some group of people who cannot perhaps afford the cost or due to mobility disabilities cannot use the full capacity of provided transport services. Therefore, it can be argued that the equity in transport as part of SWF is often not the core concern of mainstream project appraisal (Di Ciommo and Shiftan, 2017). Recently, the theoretical literature on transport equity and justice tends to focus on the concept of accessibility gain defined as the number or range of destinations that an individual can reach as an alternative replacing travel time saving in CBA. (Martens and Di Ciommo 2017, Cascetta et al., 2016; Geurs et al., 2010; Berechman, 2009, Niemeier, 1997; Recker et al., 2001).

The term social exclusion was used for the first time by former French Secretary of State for Social Action, René Lenoir (1974), to refer to the situation of certain groups of people who were considered vulnerable as not covered by social insurance systems of the welfare state. Afterwards, the concept of social inclusion has been employed in different domains including transport and mobility planning. As such, affordable transport and accessibility have been discussed by scholars as key factors decreasing exposure and vulnerability of people regarding transport-related social exclusion (TRSE), especially of those of the vulnerable-to-exclusion citizen groups (e.g. women, youths, migrants and low-income citizens³⁵). Given the increasing demand for greater attention towards mobility, the requirements brought about by the digitised transport system as well as the skills and strategies necessary and accessibility needs of disadvantaged population groups and territorial areas, there is greater need for raising awareness at EU and national/local level of the importance of transport to social inclusion. Although measuring social

³⁵

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/953951/Transport_and_inequality_report_document.pdf

exclusion is challenging due to its multidimensional aspects that extensively rely on people's current travel behaviour and mobility culture and the lack of harmonized data sources across EU member states and for all social groups³⁶, but it is recommended the additional appraisal indicators: accessibility gains and social inclusion to be accounted as part of CBA for appraisal of transport public projects funded by EU investment and the European regional development fund (ERDF), the cohesion fund (CF) and the European social fund (ESF).

5.2 Hedonic values

As stated by Ahtola (1985), the hedonic or experiential perspective is not limited to only the scope of individuals' attitude,s while it also includes the various aspects of consumer behaviour such as traveller cognitive and affective appraisal of a specific transport mode. Hedonic values are subjective and associated with pleasure experienced/perceived or anticipated from the behaviour which are results from the aesthetic/ emotional feelings such as fear, joy, boredom, like/ dislike (Holbrook and Hirschman 1982, Hirschman and Solomon, 1984 and Ahtola, 1985). In the last decades, extensive empirical studies have been accomplished regarding the hedonic valuation which reveal the significant influence of affective evaluation on users' satisfaction and behavioural intentions in a service context (Andreassen and Lindestad, 1998; Chen and Tsai, 2007; Lee et al., 2007; McDougall and Levesque, 2000; Patterson and Spreng, 1997; Pura, 2005). In the context of individuals' satisfaction, the cognitive evaluation refers to level of satisfaction with life, and the affective evaluation refers to both positive and negative individuals' hedonic evaluation, which emerges from emotions/feelings and mood as stated by scholars (Kahneman and Krueger, 2006; Kahneman et al., 1997; Oliver, 2010; Hoorn, 2007). In the mobility context, besides one's cognitive evaluation, travel satisfaction is also influenced by the affective evaluation of the traveller. It is therefore necessary to capture the affective dimension of well-being, which can be obtained by assessment scales using opposing adjectives such as depressed or happy (De Vos et al., 2015).

5.3 Health values

This value generally refers to what extent people would be willing to pay for improvement in health by observing property values with varying level of air pollution.

In the mobility context, some countries such as England and Sweden are using fitness and health benefits when appraising active travel modes. This evaluation is based on the World Health Organization Heat tool³⁷ that analyses the correlation between physical activity and life expectancy.

As evident, it can also be highlighted that some Nordic countries such as Norway, Finland, Sweden and Denmark already adjusted the national frameworks by incorporating the health values into the transport project appraisals. For instance, Finland introduced the guidelines for the assessment of walking and

³⁶ <https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/rwss/2016/chapter1.pdf>

³⁷ <https://www.euro.who.int/en/health-topics/environment-and-health/Transport-and-health/activities/guidance-and-tools/health-economic-assessment-tool-heat-for-cycling-and-walking>

cycling projects containing unit value indexes for emission costs, noise, traffic accidents, time costs and other social impacts which are also applicable for evaluating the impacts of cycling investments (Saari and Tervonen ,2007).

6 MOTIV CBA CASE STUDY

The H2020 “Mobility and Time Value” (MoTiV) project addressed emerging needs and perspectives on Value of Travel Time (VTT) adopting the travellers’ viewpoint, a relevant research area particularly valuable to decision-makers, transportation planners, engineers, and economists in the context of projects aiming at enhancing transportation infrastructure. In this respect, it did not focus only on the economic value of travel time savings, which is central to VTT studies carried out since the 1960s to support transport appraisals. Rather, it adopted a broader conceptual framework beyond time and cost saving that attempts to quantify how endogenous and exogenous factors shape the individual travel experience for various trip purposes across different transport modes, thus contributing to the sense of “wasted” or “worthwhile” travel time. This approach recognises that travel time can be used to carry out productive tasks in a wider sense, which could be in the form of paid work, fitness, or personal enjoyment. Thanks to the gathered data on perceptions of travel time across various transport modes in Belgium, Finland, France, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Slovakia and Spain using a ‘crowdsourcing’ type Woorti smartphone app devised by the consortium, the MoTiV project developed a new user-focused ‘worthwhileness index’ based on the level of productivity, fitness and enjoyment reported by the EU travellers. This index is defined as a computed measure of changes in travel experience and stand alone metrics that vary according to different factors (mode, experience factors, activities undertaken while travelling) that can be incorporated in the CBA to improve the appraisal of transport 38. From the perspective of CBA, the following contributions of MoTiV are identified:

- A novel conceptual framework that encourages the adoption of a wider perspective on the use and worthwhileness of time spent travelling, within which Worthwhile Travel Time (WTT) is defined as a function of three main factors: productivity, enjoyment, and fitness. This brings the research beyond the usual ‘productive business travel time’ and towards a more general ‘worthwhile (any) travel time’. This helps to open a new set of questions for valuation and appraisal.
- A novel approach for measuring worthwhileness of travel time and new quantitative evidence around how people perceive worthwhileness of travel time, including:
 - Ex-ante generic perception of WTT for each transport means
 - Ex-post reported perception of WTT for multiple trips, using a 1 to 5 scale (1 = verylow; 5 = very high);

³⁸ https://motivproject.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/D5.1_Cost-Benefit_Analysis_Report.pdf

- Differences across travel settings and characteristics: modes, countries (the survey was undertaken simultaneously in several countries), gender or age. Arguably, the evidence across modes is of most interest in CBA;
 - Evidence on the roles of 'enjoyment' and 'fitness' factors alongside the 'productivity' factor on the overall worthwhileness.
- A novel modelling exercise to develop an index (WI), which reveals robust evidence of the expected strong positive relationship between all proposed worthwhileness factors and WTT.

It is worth noting that the WI results of the MoTiV project could also support a more qualitative approach as complementary information for the evaluation of Benefit-Cost Ratios (BCR) of transport projects. These outcomes could be insightful for transport and mobility planners to investigate the opportunities for worthwhile travel in multimodal transport system appraisal and also for decision-makers to see evidence on how much worthwhileness is being achieved by project A compared to project B, although a monetary value is not practically available.

7 THE ROLE OF PUBLIC INTEREST

7.1 What is public interest?

To discuss the role of public interest, it would seem appropriate to first provide a definition of the notion of public interest as well as that of public policy, given that the two concepts are inherently intertwined.

Public policy can be described as the process of actualising the needs and wishes of a community into legislation, policies, actions, etc. The wishes and needs at the basis of public policy are matters which are regarded by the legislature or by the courts as being of fundamental concern to the State and the whole society³⁹, in other words, the public interest. Therefore, public policy addresses (or at least should desirably address) public interest, which represents the moral, cultural and economic values uniting a community. Public interest denotes an interest that goes beyond the interest of the individual or mere factions. A public interest can refer to both society as a whole (for example, environmental issues); to a local interest (e.g., a local railway construction project) or to a group of individuals (e.g., consumer interests).⁴⁰

It is clear that public interest is an abstract concept which is difficult to describe in an objective manner and, in reality, public interest as a concept takes shape and becomes determined when juxtaposed with a legal rule.⁴¹ However, determining what values most people in society uphold to or aspire to is also difficult (if not impossible). Of course, some are clear: murder is unacceptable, corruption is despicable

³⁹ B. A. Garner (2016), p. 729.

⁴⁰ A. J. Belohlavek (2012), p.120

⁴¹ *Ibidem* p.121

and should not have place in a fair society. In fact, there are values that in a multicultural society are more difficult to be commonly held.⁴² Values such as environmental protection in the mobility culture belong to a grey area, as they may clash with other values, such as the right to work, to free movement and also with habits of the people across the EU.

7.2 Public interest and EU law

Under EU law, the notion of public interest is difficult to define in an abstract and objective manner, since one may find this notion in various areas of EU law where it may have different meanings. Also, there seems to be no consistent and unifying definition of public interest in the jurisprudence of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU).

It should further be noted that, according to Article 17(1) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), the European Commission (Commission) in its work as institution should promote the "general interest of the Union". Therefore, any piece of legislation proposed/promoted by the Commission, any policy or proposed action shall be taken with the "general interest of the Union" in mind.

The specific interest of protecting the environment is enshrined in Articles 11 and 191 to 193 TFEU, where Article 191 explicitly indicates combating climate change as an objective of EU environmental policy.⁴³ This means that environmental protection and combating against climate change are part of EU public policy and represent some of the EU's most fundamental values. Therefore, any public interest arising within the EU should (in theory) be assessed considering these (and other) fundamental values. For example, in case the public interest of a local group living in a remote area would be to build a highway in order to be more easily connected to nearby cities, this should be assessed against the backdrop of the environmental impact the building of the highway and the increased traffic (and other environmental concerns) together with other fundamental values of the EU (and of the concerned Member State), such as the freedom of movement and the right to work.

For our analysis we will take as a starting point the EU public policy in place with regards to transport (7.3), where we will first discuss the most recent development in EU policy and legislation, the EU Green Deal (7.3.1) and then the current status of various transportation modes (air, road, rail and inland waterway), in order to assess what values have been found to be of public interest by the EU Courts and by certain pieces of EU transport legislation (7.3.2), which will help us understand how public interest has shaped (and can shape) the mobility culture. We will also explore the influence of public interest on the

⁴² P. De Jersey (2003), p. 1

⁴³ Eur-Lex, Environment and Climate Change, (https://eur-lex.europa.eu/summary/chapter/environment.html?root_default=SUM_1_CODED%3D20%2CSUM_2_CODED%3D2001&locale=en#:~:text=EU%20environment%20policy%20is%20based,objective%20of%20EU%20environmental%20policy).

fundamental freedoms of the EU (free movement of goods, free movement of persons and of workers, freedom of establishment) (7.4), the domain of State aid (7.5) and EU competition law (7.6).

7.3 EU Transport Policy

The EU Transport Policy⁴⁴ is the body of laws, implementing measures, policies, actions, etc., put in place by the EU in the area of transport. Under the TFEU, transport is an area of shared competence between the EU and its Member States.⁴⁵ In practice, this means that, in the domain of transport, both the EU and Member States may legislate and enact policies. However, Member States may exercise their competence only to the extent that it does not violate EU law relating to transport,⁴⁶ that is to say the EU common transport policy and its implementing measures.

The TFEU emphasises that transport shall be understood quite broadly, as it includes international transport to or from the territory of a Member State, as well as the providing of transport services, the improvement of transport safety and any other appropriate measures.⁴⁷

Furthermore, the TFEU also connects the domain of transport with that of Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T), which is also an area of shared competence⁴⁸. Indeed, with the development of TEN-T the EU aims to enable all EU citizens and economic operators to fully benefit from the internal market.⁴⁹

In this section we will provide a general overview to the role of public interest in EU transport legislation in order to have a better understanding of what the specific values that have been generally accepted in this regard.

The bedrock of the EU transport policy are indeed the EU's fundamental freedoms enshrined in the TFEU (free movement of people, goods, services and workers as well as freedom of establishment). In this chapter we will also provide examples of the role public interest has played in derogating from these fundamental freedoms in the transport sector with the objective to have a better view of what are the values that have been singled out also in this regard.

⁴⁴ The EU transport policy aims to provide efficient, safe and environmentally friendly mobility solutions for Europeans and to create the conditions for a competitive industry generating growth and jobs. Traffic congestion, innovation, passenger rights and funding the infrastructure are just a few examples of transport issues that are best tackled at EU-level. European Commission, Policies, Transport, (https://ec.europa.eu/info/policies/transport_en).

⁴⁵ Art. 4(2)(g) TFEU.

⁴⁶ Art. 2(2) TFEU.

⁴⁷ Art. 91(1) TFEU.

⁴⁸ Art. 4(2)(h) TFEU. The TEN-T policy addresses the implementation and development of a Europe-wide network of railway lines, roads, inland waterways, maritime shipping routes, ports, airports and railroad terminals. The ultimate objective is to close gaps, remove bottlenecks and technical barriers, as well as to strengthen social, economic and territorial cohesion in the EU. The current TEN-T policy is based on Regulation (EU) No 1315/2013. Art. 4 (2) (h) Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union.

⁴⁹ Art. 170 (1) TFEU.

7.3.1 THE EU GREEN DEAL AND PUBLIC INTEREST

When discussing the notion of public interest in EU transport legislation, it is inevitable to mention the most recent development in EU policy, i.e., the EU Green Deal⁵⁰. The EU Green Deal, presented by the Commission in December 2019, is a detailed vision to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, safeguard biodiversity, establish a circular economy and eliminate pollution, while boosting the competitiveness of European industry and ensuring a just transition for the regions and workers affected. As a mid-term goal, the Commission set the target of reducing greenhouse gases emissions by 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels.⁵¹

The EU Green Deal is the prelude and the foundation of a daunting, but necessary, environmental-centric industrial revolution. EU legislation has obviously dealt with environmental policies in the past, but the EU Green Deal is a far-reaching project that will require unprecedented investments and legislative changes.⁵² The transition envisioned in the EU Green Deal will require amendments to a wide variety of existing EU legislation and policies, including in the field of transport. In particular, the EU Green Deal envisages giving a strong boost to multimodal transport⁵³; increasing the role of automated and connected multimodal mobility together with smart traffic management systems enabled by digitalisation; and ensuring that price of transport must reflect the impact of it has on the environment and on health. Furthermore, the Commission indicates that the production and deployment of sustainable alternatives transport fuels should be developed and, more generally, that transport should become drastically less polluting, especially in cities.⁵⁴

After the approval of the Climate Law in June 2021, the Commission (in its "Fit for 55" package introduced in July 2021) presented a set of proposed legislative tools necessary to deliver the targets set in the Climate Law. These legislative tools include several proposals which will be relevant in the field of transport: the Renewable Energy Directive, which will set a target to produce 40% of all energy from renewable sources by 2030 (also in the field of transport); a proposal for a combination of measures to tackle rising emissions in road transport by cars and vans, which will require average emissions of new cars to come down by 55% from 2030 and by 100% from 2035, compared to 2021 levels. Also, the revised Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation will require Member States to expand charging capacity and to install charging and fuelling points at regular intervals on major highways (every 60km for electric charging and every 150km for hydrogen refuelling). In addition, the Alternative Fuels Infrastructure Regulation will require that aircraft and ships have access to clean electricity supply in major ports and

⁵⁰ COM(2019) 640 final, 11 December 2019, European Commission, The European Green Deal, ("EU Green Deal").

⁵¹ Art. 4, Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 June 2021 establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulations (EC) No 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999 ("European Climate Law")

⁵² S.Veschuur, C.Sbrolli (2021), p.41

⁵³ A substantial part of the 75% inland freight carried today by road should shift onto rail and inland waterways (EU Green Deal, p.10).

⁵⁴ EU Green Deal, p.11.

airports and will oblige fuel suppliers to blend increasing levels of sustainable aviation and maritime fuels in jet and maritime fuels.⁵⁵

In conclusion, the EU Green Deal marks a sharp shift in the EU's public interest objections towards a clear focus on sustainability and the environment. However, the EU Green Deal is a vision for the (near) future of the EU, and we will therefore also analyse the public interest considerations embedded in current EU transport legislation.

7.3.2 PUBLIC INTEREST IN EU TRANSPORT LEGISLATION AND POLICIES

The totality of EU legislation in the transport sector is very broad and regulates many aspects of this sector, from passengers' rights to slot assignment in airports.⁵⁶ With regards to the EU Transport policy in general, the EU and the Commission have, in the past few years, enacted and proposed a number of initiatives with the aim to create a Single European Transport Area. As indicated by the Commission in its 2019 Transport in the European Union report, the main challenges (reflecting the public interest) for the transport sector in the EU include connecting Europe with modern, multi-modal (therefore connecting, inland waterways, as well as air, road and rail in the most efficient way), safe transport infrastructure networks, and shifting towards low-emission mobility. In addition, and from a social perspective, affordability, reliability and accessibility of transport are key criteria. Indeed, addressing these challenges will help pursue sustainable growth in the EU.⁵⁷

In this wealth of provisions, the notion of public interest is not defined, however in the preambles of the different pieces of legislation it is possible to infer which values and motives underlie the relevant provisions. In the following paragraphs, various examples from EU legislation will be analysed.

7.3.2.1 *Examples of interests and values behind air transport policy*

Aviation is a strategically important sector, significantly contributing to the EU's overall economy and employment. Aviation supports almost 5 million jobs and contributes €300 billion, or 2.1%, to European GDP.⁵⁸

First and foremost, airspace, being a common resource for a wide range of users (from consumers to the military) needs to be used flexibly by all of them. Fairness and transparency should always be ensured,

⁵⁵ European Commission, European Green Deal: Commission proposes transformation of EU economy and society to meet climate ambitions (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_21_3541).

⁵⁶ A complete list of the EU transport legislation is (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/summary/chapter/32.html>).

⁵⁷ European Commission, Transport in the European Union, Current Trends and Issues, March 2019, (<https://ec.europa.eu/transport/sites/default/files/2019-transport-in-the-eu-current-trends-and-issues.pdf>).

⁵⁸ European Commission, Transport modes, Air (https://ec.europa.eu/transport/modes/air_en).

taking into account and safeguarding⁵⁹ security and defence needs.⁶⁰ Furthermore, the smooth operation of the air transport system requires that a high level of safety is maintained at all times.⁶¹

The importance of the aviation industry in the EU can be best described by these few paragraphs of Regulation 2019/712 on safeguarding competition in air transport:

"Aviation plays a crucial role in the Union's economy and in the everyday lives of Union citizens and is one of the best performing and most dynamic sectors of the Union economy. It is a strong driver for economic growth, jobs, trade and tourism, as well as connectivity and mobility for businesses and citizens alike, particularly within the Union aviation internal market. Over the past decades, growth in air transport services has significantly contributed to improving connectivity within the Union and with third countries and has been a significant enabler of the Union economy.

*Union air carriers are at the centre of a global network connecting Europe internally and with the rest of the world. They should be enabled to compete against third countries air carriers in an environment of open and fair competition. This is necessary in order to bring benefits to consumers, to maintain conditions conducive to a high level of Union air connectivity and to ensure transparency, a level-playing field and continuing competitiveness of Union air carriers, as well as high levels of quality employment in the Union aviation industry."*⁶²

From the paragraphs above the most important interests underlying aviation policy are apparent: the need for economic growth and for the wealth generated by the industry (in the form of aviation-related jobs, trade and tourism), the need for connectivity; and the need to ensure a level-playing field and fair competition between air carriers (which, ultimately, leads to more choice for consumers).

However, all these interests and values in the aviation industry must be weighed against the industry's environmental impact, as indicated in the EU Aviation Strategy:

*"[...] Growth in air traffic in Europe and worldwide needs to be reconciled with maintaining high standards of aviation safety and security, as well as reducing aviation's environmental footprint and contributing to the fight against climate change. In short, aviation must grow in a sustainable manner."*⁶³

⁵⁹ Commission Regulation (EU) No 255/2010 of 25 March 2010 laying down common rules on air traffic flow management, paragraph 5.

⁶⁰ Regulation (EC) No 551/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 March 2004 on the organisation and use of the airspace in the single European sky (the airspace Regulation), paragraph 6.

⁶¹ Regulation (EC) No 549/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 March 2004 laying down the framework for the creation of the single European sky (the framework Regulation), paragraph 3.

⁶² Regulation (EU) 2019/712 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on safeguarding competition in air transport, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 868/2004, paragraphs 1 and 2.

⁶³ COM(2015) 598 final, 7 December 2015, Communication From The Commission To The European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic And Social Committee And The Committee Of The Regions, An Aviation Strategy for Europe, paragraph 1.1.

The Commission further indicates in its Aviation Strategy⁶⁴ that the EU must be a leading player in international aviation and a global model for sustainable aviation, with a high level of service and ambitious EU standards. In addition, the Commission identifies three key priorities for aviation within the EU:

- Tapping into growth markets, by improving services, market access and investment opportunities with third countries, whilst guaranteeing a level playing field;
- Tackling limits to growth in the air and on the ground, by reducing capacity constraints and improving efficiency and connectivity;
- Maintaining high EU safety and security standards, by shifting to a risk and performance-based mind-set.

The Commission acknowledges that *"Contributing to a resilient Energy Union and a forward-looking Climate Change Policy"* is an area where EU actions are needed, however it was not listed as one of the three key priorities.

Other highly relevant public interests in connection with the aviation industry include the Air Passengers' Rights Regulation⁶⁵, where it is established that consumers should be afforded a high level of protection. Passengers flying by air shall, among others, receive compensation or re-routing in case of cancellation of their flight, and be compensated in case of denied boarding. Only in the event of extraordinary and unavoidable circumstances can the obligations imposed upon air carriers be lifted. While the public interest represented by all of the EU passengers is quite clear, it could be argued that the high level of consumer rights for EU passengers, together with low pricing policies, and deregulation since the late 1980s⁶⁶ created a culture of fast and carefree travel within the EU which has become unsustainable.

7.3.2.2 Examples of interests and values behind road transport policy

The aim of the EU's land transport policy is to promote mobility that is efficient, safe, secure and environmentally friendly. The EU's policy objectives for road transport include promoting an efficient road freight and passenger transport services; and guaranteeing effective and just application of the road transport rules.⁶⁷

⁶⁴ *Ibidem*, paragraph 1.2.

⁶⁵ Regulation (EC) No 261/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 February 2004 establishing common rules on compensation and assistance to passengers in the event of denied boarding and of cancellation or long delay of flights, and repealing Regulation (EEC) No 295/91.

⁶⁶ G. Burghouwt, et al. (2015), p.7.

⁶⁷ European Commission, Transport modes, Road (https://ec.europa.eu/transport/modes/road_en).

The first interest of public relevance to be taken into account concerning road transport, as for any other type of transport, is safety. However, in road transport the safety aspect is more enhanced than for other types of transport as there is a much higher concentration of non-transport professionals operating on the same routes as transport professionals (there are many more people driving cars on highways alongside truck drivers than amateur planes flying alongside aircrafts). In addition, the vast majority of transport within the EU is made by road⁶⁸, intensifying the risks and concentration of traffic.

Safety on roads is ensured by EU citizens and transport professionals abiding by traffic rules alike. However, transport professionals have specific rules applying to them⁶⁹ in order to ensure safety on the roads as well as good working conditions for drivers and to avoid distortions of competition. These rules dictate the transport professionals' working and resting times (both daily and weekly).⁷⁰

Another interesting example of public interest regarding road transport can be found in the Directive on the promotion of clean and energy-efficient road transport vehicles⁷¹. This Directive applies to procurement contracts and requires Member States to ensure that contracting authorities and contracting entities consider lifetime energy and environmental impacts, including energy consumption and emissions of CO₂ and of certain pollutants, when procuring certain road transport vehicles. This complies with the objectives of promoting and stimulating the market for clean and energy-efficient vehicles, even if only applying to procurement procedures, and of improving the contribution of the transport sector to the environment, climate and energy policies of the EU.⁷²

7.3.2.3 Examples of interests and values behind rail transport policy

The Commission has set the objective to strengthen the rail transport market in the EU, both for freight and for passengers. The Commission indicated that the most crucial areas for developing a strong and competitive rail transport industry include opening the rail transport market to competition; improving the interoperability and safety of national networks; and developing rail transport infrastructure.⁷³ With the adoption of the so-called Railway packages (2001-2016), the Commission aimed at gradually opening

⁶⁸ Between 2008 and 2019 more than 70% of transport has been done via road, whereas only about 5% is done via inland waterways and around 18% by rail. Source: Eurostat (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Freight_transport_statistics_-_modal_split)

⁶⁹ Regulation (EC) No 561/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 March 2006 on the harmonisation of certain social legislation relating to road transport and amending Council Regulations (EEC) No 3821/85 and (EC) No 2135/98 and repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No 3820/85.

⁷⁰ Due to the Covid-19 pandemic and the increase in delivery of goods, certain Member States have implemented temporary exceptions to these rules specifically in the field of commercial road transport (https://ec.europa.eu/transport/modes/road/social_provisions/driving_time_en)

⁷¹ Directive 2009/33/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 April 2009 on the promotion of clean and energy-efficient road transport vehicles.

⁷² *Ibidem*, Art. 1.

⁷³ European Commission, Transport modes, Rail (https://ec.europa.eu/transport/modes/rail_en).

up rail transport service markets for competition, making national railways systems interoperable, and defining the conditions for the development of a single European railway area.⁷⁴

The situation of the rail market before the first Railway package is best described in the Commission White Paper of 30 July 1996, which set out how the railway sector is in decline and its market share is falling. While at the time rail was felt not to respond to market changes or customers' needs, today's rail has characteristics that could make it an increasingly attractive form of transport in Europe. Many possibilities already exist for improving and developing services and new areas of opportunity may open up. To meet these challenges, the EU needs a new kind of railway, which is in the public interest.⁷⁵

For example, in the Directive on the interoperability of the rail system within the EU the following is stated: the Commission clearly underlines that standardisation in rail transport would be in the interest of the EU: *"An international system of standardisation capable of generating standards which are actually used by those involved in international trade and which meet the requirements of Union policy would be in the Union's interest. The European standardisation organisations should therefore continue their cooperation with international standardisation bodies."*⁷⁶

Despite the efforts of the Railway packages, rail transport is still struggling to achieve its potential, notwithstanding its comparative advantages over medium and long distances (speed and comfort for passengers and economies of scale for freight) and its potential contribution towards decarbonisation and socially inclusive mobility. This is due to a number of factors including: a lack of effective competition in many EU countries; the need for achieving technical interoperability, and discrimination faced by new market entrants in obtaining access to rail infrastructure and essential service facilities.⁷⁷

7.3.2.4 Examples of interests and values behind inland waterway policy

With more than 37,000 kilometres of waterways connecting hundreds of cities and industrial regions, inland waterway transport plays an important role for the transport of goods in Europe. Inland waterway transport is reliable, energy efficient and with significant growth potential. Unlike other types of transport, inland waterway does not suffer from problems of congestion and capacity. Therefore, the potential for increasing the modal share of inland waterway transport is significant. For these reasons, it is the

⁷⁴ European Commission, Rail, Railway packages (https://ec.europa.eu/transport/modes/rail/packages_en)

⁷⁵ European Commission White Paper: A strategy for revitalising the Community's railways, 22 January 2007 (<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/237977fb-4c54-4dcf-828c-10be15951fe1/language-en/format-HTML/source-search>)

⁷⁶ Directive (EU) 2016/797 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 May 2016 on the interoperability of the rail system within the European Union, paragraph 36.

⁷⁷ European Commission, Transport in the European Union, Current Trends and Issues, March 2019, (<https://ec.europa.eu/transport/sites/default/files/2019-transport-in-the-eu-current-trends-and-issues.pdf>).

Commission's aim to promote and strengthen the competitive position of inland waterways in the transport system and to facilitate its integration into the intermodal logistics chain.⁷⁸

This aim of the Commission is evident in its 1996 Directive concerning systems of chartering and pricing in national and international inland waterway transport where it is stated:

"... the growing problems of road and rail saturation, transport safety, environment, energy saving and quality of life of the citizen call, in the public interest, for greater development and better use of the transport potential offered by inland waterway, in particular by improving its competitiveness"⁷⁹.

This Directive called for an adjustment of the inland waterways transport to an organization of chartering by rotation⁸⁰ to move towards a system of freedom of chartering and pricing which would entail greater commercial flexibility.⁸¹

The body of legislation governing inland waterways policy is rich⁸² and regulates different aspects of this mode of transport, including the employment market, the technical features/requirements of the vessels themselves and the environment. However, despite its regulatory efforts, the Commission noted that inland waterway transport is set to lose its comparative advantage, unless structural changes are made to improve the quality of the operating conditions. This would require the definition of common standards at EU level and cross-border cooperation between EU countries.⁸³

7.4 Public interest – when can it justify derogations from fundamental freedoms?

A transport policy (whether at local level, Member State level or EU level) may relate to the transportation of goods and persons across EU internal borders, but also to the provision of transport services from an EU country to another. To achieve such a policy, authorities must take into account the free movement of goods, persons and services, as implied by the EU internal market rules.⁸⁴ However, in some cases a transport policy may have the effect of restricting these freedoms, rather than enhancing them. In any event, to be justified, such restrictions need to be based on public interest considerations. In the next

⁷⁸ European Commission, Transport modes, Inland waterways (https://ec.europa.eu/transport/modes/inland_en)

⁷⁹ Council Directive 96/75/EC of 19 November 1996 on the systems of chartering and pricing in national and international inland waterway transport in the Community.

⁸⁰ This is a system which consists of allocating in a charter exchange requests for transport operations (at previously fixed prices and under conditions made known) from customers on the basis of the order in which vessels become available after unloading. Carriers are asked, in the order of their registration on the rota, to choose in turn a load from those on offer. Those who make no choice nonetheless keep their position in the order, Directive 96/75/EC, Article 1(a).

⁸¹ *Ibidem*.

⁸² A full list of legislation can be found here:

https://ec.europa.eu/transport/sites/default/files/legislation/summary_of_eu_legislation_in_the_field_of_inland_waterways.pdf

⁸³ European Commission, Transport in the European Union, Current Trends and Issues, March 2019

(<https://ec.europa.eu/transport/sites/default/files/2019-transport-in-the-eu-current-trends-and-issues.pdf>).

⁸⁴ Art. 26, TFEU.

few paragraphs, we will discuss such public interest considerations with regards to each of the fundamental freedoms.

7.4.1.1 Free movement of goods

The free movement of goods between EU Member State is one of the fundamental principles of the TFEU.⁸⁵ It aims to remove trade barriers between Member States, by eliminating custom duties, quantitative restrictions and measures having an equivalent effect to quantitative restrictions⁸⁶ (including discriminatory taxation)⁸⁷. Therefore, public interest considerations can justify proportionate restrictions of the free movement of goods, however, these considerations shall not constitute a means of arbitrary discrimination or a disguised restriction on trade between Member States.⁸⁸

Indeed, some objectives of public interest are capable of taking precedence over the free movement of goods and allowing non-financial obstacles to the latter,⁸⁹ as long as they fall within either one of the grounds laid down in Article 36 TFEU or imperative requirements recognised by case-law.⁹⁰ In addition, to be fully justified the measure also needs to be both appropriate to achieve the objective at hand and not go beyond what is necessary to attain it.⁹¹

In addition to the grounds laid down in Article 36 of the TFEU (public morality; public policy or public security; the protection of health and life of humans, animals or plants; the protection of national treasures possessing artistic, historic or archaeological value; the protection of industrial and commercial property), case-law in the domain of transport recognised the following objectives as being of public interest:

- Combatting noise pollution.⁹² Germany introduced a new law making the first registration in Germany of aircrafts previously registered in another Member State conditional upon compliance with stricter noise standards than those laid down by EU legislation on the limitation of noise emissions from subsonic aircraft (while exempting from those standards aircraft which obtained registration in Germany before this piece of EU legislation was implemented). Although this measure was considered an obstacle to the free movement of goods, the CJEU held that it was compatible with EU law, since it was not disproportionate and was supported by an objective of public interest enhancing public health and environmental protection, i.e. the objective of combatting noise pollution.

⁸⁵ European Parliament, Fact Sheets on the European Union, Free movement of goods, (<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/38/free-movement-of-goods>).

⁸⁶ Title II, Chapter 3, TFEU.

⁸⁷ Art. 110, TFEU.

⁸⁸ Art. 36, TFEU.

⁸⁹ Case C-525/14, *Commission v Czech Republic*, [2016], ECLI:EU:C:2016:714, para. 35.

⁹⁰ Case C-663/18, *Request for a preliminary ruling from the Cour d'appel d'Aix-En-Provence* [2020], EU:C:2020:938, para. 83.

⁹¹ *Ibidem*.

⁹² Case C-389/96, *Aher-Waggon GmbH v Federal Republic of Germany* [1998], EU:C:1998:357, paras. 19-25.

- Reduction of pollutants.⁹³ Austria prohibited lorries of over 7.5 tonnes carrying certain goods from using a specific section of a motorway in order to reduce emissions of atmospheric pollutants. The CJEU held that, although this measure was supported by the public interest of protecting the environment, it was disproportionate and therefore not compatible with the free movement of goods. Indeed, according to the CJEU, Austria should have examined more carefully the possibility of using measures less restrictive of the freedom of movement. Instead of adopting such a total traffic ban, Austria could have reached the objective of protecting the environment by either extending the traffic prohibition for lorries in certain Euro classes to lorries in other classes or replacing the variable speed limit with a permanent 100 km/h speed limit.

7.4.1.2 Free movement of persons and of workers

Free movement of workers, one of the fundamental principles of the EU since its inception, prohibits any discrimination based on nationality as regards employment, remuneration and other conditions of work and employment. Workers also have the right to move freely within the Member State where they are working, to remain in the host State for the purpose of employment and to prolong their stay, provided that certain conditions are fulfilled.⁹⁴ Also the free movement of workers⁹⁵ and, more generally, the free movement of EU citizens can be limited pursuant to public interest considerations.⁹⁶

Indeed, for workers, a transport policy may hinder or render less attractive the exercise of their free movement if it pursues a legitimate objective in the public interest.⁹⁷ Such an objective needs to fall within the legitimate aims laid down in Article 45 TFEU.⁹⁸ In addition, to be fully justified, the measure in question also needs to be both appropriate to achieve the objective and not go beyond what is necessary to attain it.⁹⁹

For example, the CJEU considered that the legitimate aims laid down in Article 45 TFEU were not fulfilled by Belgian legislation requiring all employers having their place of business located in Belgium to draft cross-border employment contracts (with employees domiciled in other countries) in the official language of the Belgian region where the employer was based (e.g., Dutch for Flanders and French for Wallonia).

⁹³ Case C-28/09, *Commission v Republic of Austria* [2011], EU:C:2011:854, paras. 118-150.

⁹⁴ European Parliament, Fact Sheets on the European Union, Free Movement of workers, (<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/41/free-movement-of-workers>)

⁹⁵ Art. 45, TFEU.

⁹⁶ Directive 2004/38/EC on the right of citizens of the Union, OJ L158 (2004), p. 77-123, where, for example, at Art. 27 it is indicated that Member States may restrict the freedom of movement and residence of Union citizens and their family members, irrespective of nationality, on grounds of public policy, public security or public health. For such a restriction to take place, the personal conduct of the individual concerned must **represent a genuine, present and sufficiently serious threat affecting one of the fundamental interests of society**.

⁹⁷ Case C-202/11, *Anton Las v PSA Antwerp NV* [2013], EU:C:2013:239, para. 23.

⁹⁸ Case C-710/18, *WN v Land Niedersachsen* [2020], EU:C:2020:299, para. 34.

⁹⁹ *Ibidem*.

The CJEU held that parties to a cross-border employment contract do not necessarily have knowledge of the official language of the Member State concerned, hindering free and informed consent.¹⁰⁰

In another case, the regional authorities of a German state (*Land*) denied payment of the costs of transport to school after the family of the student in question relocated their residence from the Land to another Member State (France). The CJEU notably held that practical difficulties linked to the effective organisation of school transport within a Land do not constitute an overriding reason of public interest that can justify a national measure categorised as indirect discrimination.¹⁰¹

More generally, a transport policy may restrict the freedom of movement and residence of EU citizens, if it pursues particular objectives of public interest. The EU Citizens' Rights Directive identifies public policy, public security, and public health as such objectives.¹⁰² Measures taken on grounds of public policy (or public security) have to comply with the principles of proportionality and shall be based exclusively on the personal conduct of the individual concerned. In practice, the individuals concerned must represent a genuine and sufficiently serious threat affecting one of the fundamental interests of society.¹⁰³ The freedom of movement and residence for persons in the EU was established in the Treaty of Maastricht and forms the fundamental basis for 'Union citizenship'.

7.4.1.3 Free movement of services and freedom of establishment

Finally, the freedom of establishment¹⁰⁴ and the freedom to provide services¹⁰⁵ between Member States may also be limited by public interest considerations. The **freedom of establishment** includes – among other things - the right to take up and pursue activities as a self-employed person¹⁰⁶, and the **freedom to provide services** includes the freedom to provide various services in the field of transport,¹⁰⁷ including

¹⁰⁰ Case C-202/11, *Anton Las v PSA Antwerp NV* [2013], EU:C:2013:239, paras 23-34.

¹⁰¹ Case C-830/18, *Landkreis Südliche Weinstraße v PF and Others* [2020], para 46.

¹⁰² Directive 2004/38/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 29 April 2004 on the right of citizens of the Union and their family members to move and reside freely within the territory of the Member States amending Regulation (EEC) No 1612/68 and repealing Directives 64/221/EEC, 68/360/EEC, 72/194/EEC, 73/148/EEC, 75/34/EEC, 75/35/EEC, 90/364/EEC, 90/365/EEC and 93/96/EEC, Art. 27 (and following).

¹⁰³ *Ibidem*, Art. 27(2).

¹⁰⁴ Art. 49 (and following), TFEU.

¹⁰⁵ Art. 56 (and following), TFEU.

¹⁰⁶ Art. 49 TFEU.

¹⁰⁷ Art. 58 TFEU.

air services,¹⁰⁸ maritime cabotage services,¹⁰⁹ maritime transport services,¹¹⁰ international coach and bus services¹¹¹ and rail services.¹¹²

Nevertheless, as mentioned above, a transport policy may prohibit, impede or render less attractive the exercise of the freedom of establishment and the freedom to provide services,¹¹³ if such restrictions can be justified by a legitimate objective of public interest.¹¹⁴ One may consider an objective as being a legitimate objective of public interest, if the latter falls within both the grounds laid down in Articles 51 and 62 TFEU or imperative requirements recognised by case-law.¹¹⁵ Finally, to be fully justified, the measure supported by such an objective needs to be both appropriate to achieve the objective and not go beyond what is necessary to attain it.¹¹⁶

Case-law in the domain of transport notably has recognised following objectives as being legitimate objectives of public interest:

- Ensuring safety in port areas.¹¹⁷ Belgium introduced an obligation for persons or undertakings wishing to carry out port activities in a port area to have recourse only to dockers recognised by Belgian legislation. This measure, however, prevented companies from Member States other than Belgium from using their own dockers.

Such legislation thus constituted a restriction of the freedom of establishment and the freedom to provide services. Nonetheless, this restriction may be justified by the objective of ensuring safety in port areas. However, to be fully justified, the national court needed to assess whether such legislation did not impose unreasonable and disproportionate administrative burdens.

¹⁰⁸ Under Art. 2 (4) of the Air Services Regulation (Regulation (EC) No 1008/2008), it means a flight or a series of flights carrying passengers, cargo and/or mail for remuneration and/or hire.

¹⁰⁹ Under Art. 2 (1) of the Maritime Cabotage Regulation (Regulation (EEC) No 3577/92), it relates to mainland cabotage, off-shore supply services and island cabotage provided for remuneration.

¹¹⁰ Under Art. 1 (4) Maritime Transport Regulation (Regulation (EEC) No 4055/86), it relates to intra-Community shipping services and third-country traffic provided for remuneration.

¹¹¹ Under Art. 2 Coach and Bus Services Regulation (Regulation (EC) No 1073/2009), it includes (among others) a journey undertaken by a vehicle to carry passengers and the point of departure and the point of arrival of which are in two different Member States, with or without transit through one or more Member States or third countries.

¹¹² Under Art. 3 (1) of the Single European Railway Area Directive (Directive 2012/34/EU), it includes (among others) services provided by undertakings, whose business is to provide services for the transport of goods and/or passengers by rail with a requirement that the undertaking ensure traction.

¹¹³ Joined Cases C-407/19 and C-471/19, *Katoen Natie Bulk Terminals NV and General Services Antwerp NV v Belgische Staat and Middlegate Europe NV v Ministerraad* [2021], EU:C:2021:107, para. 58.

¹¹⁴ Case C-465/18, *AV and BU v Comune di Bernareggio* [2019], EU:C:2019:1125, para. 44.

¹¹⁵ Case C-225/15, *Criminal proceedings against Domenico Politanò Request for a preliminary ruling from the Tribunale di Reggio Calabria* [2016], EU:C:2016:645, para. 41.

¹¹⁶ Joined Cases C-407/19 and C-471/19, *Katoen Natie Bulk Terminals NV and General Services Antwerp NV v Belgische Staat and Middlegate Europe NV v Ministerraad* [2021], EU:C:2021:107, para. 61.

¹¹⁷ Joined Cases C-407/19 and C-471/19, *Katoen Natie Bulk Terminals NV and General Services Antwerp NV v Belgische Staat and Middlegate Europe NV v Ministerraad* [2021], EU:C:2021:107.

- Protection of workers.¹¹⁸ A shipping company wanted to reflag one of its ships, sailing the route Helsinki and Tallinn, from Finnish to Estonian flag in order to be able to enter into a new collective agreement with a trade union established in Estonia and to employ a crew based on Estonian wages, which were significantly lower than in Finland.¹¹⁹ A trade union initiated a collective action, announcing its intention to strike, to prevent the shipping company from reflagging. In addition, an international workers' federation sent a circular to its affiliates asking them not to enter into negotiations with the shipping company and, as a result, the shipping company was prevented from engaging talks with Estonian trade unions. The shipping company then sought an injunction in court as the trade union's action together with the international workers' federation hindered its freedom of establishment. The CJEU ruled that the right to strike and take collective action is recognised as a fundamental right in the EU, but this right has to be reconciled with the freedom of establishment. It was for the national court to determine whether in this particular case the alleged restriction of the freedom of establishment was justified by overriding reason of public interest, such as the protection of workers.

7.5 Public Interest and State Aid

A company that receives government support, i.e., State aid, gains an advantage over its competitors. Therefore, the TFEU¹²⁰ generally prohibits State aid unless it is justified by, amongst other things, reasons of general economic development.

The notion of public interest in transport policy may play a role in the application of EU State aid rules, where it is most often referred to as a "common interest" or as a "services of general interest"¹²¹, that is, services that public authorities of the Member States classify as being of general interest and, therefore, subject to specific public service obligations.¹²²

7.5.1 COMMON INTEREST

As regards the notion of common interest, this is typically applied while determining whether an aid may derogate from the general prohibition of State aid.¹²³ In this case, what needs to be assessed is whether the aid either meets the needs of coordination of transport or represents reimbursement for the discharge

¹¹⁸ Case C-438/05, *International Transport Workers' Federation and Finnish Seamen's Union v Viking Line ABP and OÜ Viking Line Eesti* [2007], EU:C:2007:772.

¹¹⁹ The Estonian crews were so much cheaper that it was more difficult for vessels operating on the Helsinki-Tallinn line under the Finnish flag (and therefore under Finnish law labour conditions) to be competitive against Estonian crews.

¹²⁰ Art. 107, TFEU.

¹²¹ Preamble, Protocol No 26 annexed to the TFEU.

¹²² European Commission, A Quality Framework for Services of General Interest in Europe, COM(2011) 900 final, p. 3.

¹²³ Art. 107 (1) TFEU.

of certain public service obligations.¹²⁴ The latter case falls within the Services of General Economic Interest, which will be discussed below.

Regarding **the coordination of transport**, the settled decisional practice of the Commission has emphasised that, to fall within the scope of this category, the aid needs to contribute to an objective of common interest.¹²⁵ By way of example, the Commission considered the following State aids to be compatible with the internal market on this ground:

- The objective of encouraging the modal shift to rail, since the State aid at issue aimed to ensure the technical and operational interconnection of railway systems.¹²⁶ Indeed, one of the fundamental goals of the proposed measure was the strengthening of competitiveness of railway transport against road transport. In addition, apart from the contribution to this objective, this scheme also fulfilled all other criteria, with regard to Article 93 of the TFEU.
- The objective of coordination of transport, since the State aid at issue was to contribute to the efficient and smooth provision of public transport.¹²⁷ Indeed, in the 2013 guidelines for the development of the trans-European transport network laid down in Regulation (EU) No 1315/2013, the European Commission has defined the optimal integration and interconnection of all transport modes as a key objective of the EU. In addition, apart from the contribution to such an objective of common interest, this scheme also fulfilled all other criteria with regard to Article 93 of the TFEU.

7.5.2 SERVICES OF GENERAL ECONOMIC INTEREST

Services of general interest also include **services of general economic interest**, that is to say economic activities which deliver outcomes in the overall public good that would not be provided by the market without public intervention.¹²⁸

However, being qualified as a service of general economic interest, they have important effects, since an entity entrusted with such services shall be subject to the rules contained in the Treaties, including State aid rules, only in so far as the application of such rules does not obstruct the performance of the particular tasks assigned to them.¹²⁹ In other words, derogations from Treaty rules are available provided these are necessary for the performance of a service of general economic interest.¹³⁰

¹²⁴ Art. 93 TFEU.

¹²⁵ European Commission, *State Aid SA.55861 (2019/N) – Czech republic*, C(2020) 1085 final, para. 29 (p. 5).

¹²⁶ European Commission, *State Aid SA.55861 (2019/N) – Czech republic*, C(2020) 1085 final, para. 32-35 (p. 6-7).

¹²⁷ European Commission, *State aid SA.23216 (C 54/2007) – Germany*, C(2016) 6232 final, para. 178-189 (p. 28-30).

¹²⁸ European Commission, *A Quality Framework for Services of General Interest in Europe*, COM(2011) 900 final, p. 3.

¹²⁹ Art. 106 (2) TFEU.

¹³⁰ Case C-660/15 P, *Viasat Broadcasting UK Ltd v European Commission* [2017] EU:C:2017:178, para. 29.

The link between general interest and transport policy may be present when a transport policy requires implementation of a service of general economic interest. Indeed, the term "services of general economic interest" refers to services of an economic nature which the Member States or the EU have made subject to specific public service obligations by virtue of a general interest criterion.¹³¹ Nonetheless, the Commission may not provide a list of criteria to determine the general interest of a service, as only Member States authorities may determine whether a service is in the general interest.¹³² Although Member States enjoy a wide discretion on this point, the Commission can still call this decision into question in case of a manifest error¹³³ or harmonisation at EU level in the sector at issue.¹³⁴ In the domain of transport, the following services have been considered as services of general economic interest:

- Transporting mail for the benefit of all users throughout the territory of the Member State at uniform tariffs and on similar conditions as to quality.¹³⁵
- Transporting sick or injured persons in emergencies throughout the territory of the Member State, at uniform rates and on similar quality conditions, without regard to the particular situations or to the degree of economic profitability of each individual operation.¹³⁶
- Mooring operations in ports, since mooring groups are obliged to provide at any time and to any user a universal mooring service, for reasons of safety in port waters.¹³⁷

Regarding **compensation for the fulfilment of public service obligation**, the Commission has emphasised that, to fall within this category, the aid needs to be granted for the provision of a genuine and clearly defined public service.¹³⁸ This definition only applies to transport services by rail and by road.¹³⁹ According to the Regulation on public passenger transport, a public service obligation can consist of a requirement defined or determined by a competent authority in order to ensure public passenger transport services in the general interest, that an operator - if it were considering its own commercial

¹³¹ Opinion of Advocate-General Hogan, Case C-523/18, EU:C:2019:769, para. 35.

¹³² European Commission, Guide to the application of the European Union rules on state aid, public procurement and the internal market to services of general economic interest, and in particular to social services of general interest, SWD (2013) 53 final/2, p. 23. See also: Art. 1 of the Protocol No 26 to the TFEU.

¹³³ Joined Cases C-66/16 P to C-69/16 P, *Comunidad Autónoma del País Vasco and Others v European Commission* [2017], EU:C:2017:999, para. 70.

¹³⁴ Joined Cases T-463/13 and T-464/13 *Comunidad Autónoma de Galicia and Redes de Telecomunicación Galegas Retegal, SA (Retegal) v European Commission* [2015], EU:T:2015:901, para. 95.

¹³⁵ Joined Cases C-83/01 P, C-93/01 P and C-94/01 P, *Chronopost SA, La Poste and French Republic v Union française de l'express (Ufex), DHL International, Federal express international (France) SNC and CRIE SA* [2003], EU:C:2003:388, para. 34.

¹³⁶ Case C-475/99, *Firma Ambulanz Glöckner v Landkreis Südwestpfalz* [2001], EU:C:2001:577, para. 55.

¹³⁷ Case C-266/96, *Corsica Ferries France SA v Gruppo Antichi Ormeggiatori del porto di Genova Coop. arl, Gruppo Ormeggiatori del Golfo di La Spezia Coop. arl and Ministero dei Trasporti e della Navigazione* [1998], EU:C:1998:306, para. 45.

¹³⁸ European Commission, *State Aid SA.34403 (2015/NN) – United Kingdom*, C(2015) 3657 final, para. 56 (p. 10).

¹³⁹ Regulation (EC) No 1370/2007 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2007 on public passenger transport services by rail and by road and repealing Council Regulations (EEC) Nos 1191/69 and 1107/70, Art. 1(2).

interests - would not assume to the same extent or under the same conditions without additional compensation.¹⁴⁰ By way of example, in the domain of transport the Commission considered following State aids to be compatible with the internal market on this ground:

- Not-for-profit transport services for particular groups of users unable to make effective use of conventional transport.¹⁴¹ The Commission considered that these services should be provided in ways that take account of the specific needs of these particular users (for example, school pupils living outside the regular bus route or foreseeing a call-bus service off-peak hours) and thus require significant resources. In addition, such users are often also economically disadvantaged and have limited ability to fund the services they require. As such, this service was to be seen as a public service because an economic operator - if it were considering its own commercial interests - would not provide equivalent services under similar conditions.
- Bus and tram services offering reduced rates to pupils, students and trainees.¹⁴² The Commission considered that the measure at issue aimed at ensuring open access to education as the services provide cheap public transport tickets to pupils, students, and trainees for their transportation to their schools, universities, and training places. Furthermore, this measure pursued specific social aims by financially disburdening families with children as well as environmental aims by supporting public transport, which is more eco-friendly than individual motor car transport. Since an economic operator - if it were considering its own commercial interests - would not provide equivalent services under similar conditions, this service was to be seen as a public service.

7.6 Public interest and EU competition rules

Furthermore, the notion of public interest in transport policy may interact with EU competition rules (Articles 101 and 102 TFEU).

As an example¹⁴³, the notion of public interest was crucial in a German case where national road-haulage tariffs were fixed by a committee whose members were, among other things, representatives of the economic operators in the road-haulage sector. In this case it was argued that, indeed, such tariffs may infringe the EU's *effet utile* (or useful effect) norm¹⁴⁴ by depriving State rules of the character of State

¹⁴⁰ *Ibidem*, Art. 2 (e).

¹⁴¹ European Commission, *State Aid SA.34403 (2015/NN) – United Kingdom*, C(2015) 3657 final, para. 38-40 (p. 6-7).

¹⁴² European Commission, *State Aid SA.34155 (2013/N) - Germany*, C(2014) 133 cor., para. 41-45 (p. 9-10).

¹⁴³ For more examples of cases of this kind, see *Delta* (C-153/93), *Spediporto* (C-96/94) and *Librandi* (C-38/97).

¹⁴⁴ This means that all provisions of EU law aim to have a practical effect and must, therefore, always be interpreted restrictively, with a view to achieve the intent of the legislation.

legislation by delegating to private economic operators' responsibility for taking decisions affecting the economic sphere.¹⁴⁵

The CJEU decided that road-haulage tariffs submitted to the State by a committee whose members are, among other things, representatives of the economic operators concerned that they can be compatible with EU *effet utile* norm provided that these representatives are independent experts (and do not act as representatives of the industry) entrusted with the task of fixing the tariffs on the basis of considerations of public interest. Public authorities should ensure that the committee fixes the road-haulage tariffs by reference to consideration of public interest and, if this is not done, they should intervene and decide instead of the committee.¹⁴⁶

From a terminological point of view, the CJEU in this case addressed public interest criteria by making indiscriminately reference to either the term "general interest criteria or the term "public interest criteria".¹⁴⁷ Indeed, according to the CJEU, both these designations have the same meaning and refer to taking account of interests other than those of the economic agents represented on the committee fixing road-haulage tariffs.¹⁴⁸ However, in the English version of the of the CJEU rulings, this distinction does not appear and the term "public interest" has always been the one used.¹⁴⁹ Nevertheless, this distinction is consistently made in several other language versions of the judgment, such as French ("intérêt general" and "intérêt public"), German ("allgemeines Wohl" and "Gemeinwohl"), Italian ("interesse generale" and "interesse pubblico") and Dutch ("algemeen belang" and "openbaar belang").¹⁵⁰

Regardless of the designation used, to determine whether such a tariff system observes public interest criteria, the CJEU has emphasised that EU law does not define the concept of public interest in such matter.¹⁵¹ In practice, it is for the Member States to determine the criteria which best allow the EU competition rules to be observed, while it is for the national courts to determine whether the public-interest criteria defined in the national legislation are observed in practice.¹⁵²

¹⁴⁵ Case C-185/91, *Bundesanstalt für den Güterfernverkehr v Gebrüder Reiff GmbH&Co. KG* [1993] EU:C:1993:886, para. 14.

¹⁴⁶ *Ibidem*, para. 24.

¹⁴⁷ Case C-38/97, *Autotrasporti Librandi Snc di Librandi F. & C. v Cuttica spedizioni e servizi internazionali Srl* [1998], EU:C:1998:454, para. 41.

¹⁴⁸ *Ibidem*, para. 39.

¹⁴⁹ See Case C-185/91 (*Bundesanstalt für den Güterfernverkehr v Gebrüder Reiff GmbH&Co. KG*) para. 24; Case C-153/93 (*Bundesrepublik Deutschland v Delta Schifffahrts- und Speditionsgesellschaft mbH*), para. 23; Case C-96/94 (*Centro Servizi Spediporto Srl v Spedizioni Marittima del Golfo Srl*), para. 42.

¹⁵⁰ For the use of the term "general interest" see Case C-185/91 (*Bundesanstalt für den Güterfernverkehr v Gebrüder Reiff GmbH&Co. KG*) para. 24 and Case C-153/93 (*Bundesrepublik Deutschland v Delta Schifffahrts- und Speditionsgesellschaft mbH*), para. 23. For the use of the term "public interest": Case C-96/94 (*Centro Servizi Spediporto Srl v Spedizioni Marittima del Golfo Srl*), para. 42.

¹⁵¹ Case C-38/97 (*Librandi*), para. 48.

¹⁵² Case C-38/97, (*Librandi*), paras. 46-47.

8 CONCLUSION

The development of a sustainable multimodal mobility is one of the key challenges for European cities and functional urban areas¹⁵³. Therefore to acquire European funds for the sustainable mobility system a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) is explicitly required, among other elements. The CBA is required as a basis for decision making on the co-financing of major projects included in operational programmes (OPs) of the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the Cohesion Fund¹⁵⁴.

Even if there is a general agreement on use of CBA at the EU level (which requires each factor to be valued in a monetary sense for public transport project appraisals), there is a sizeable variation concerning the inclusion of dominant values, such as travel time-saving across EU Member States; and high level of consensus on the necessity of the direct impacts as part of CBA in transport appraisal. However, what is currently paid less attention to in EU legislation and policies on inclusiveness is putting citizens at the center of mobility planning at the national level and at the EU level. This requires a more comprehensive understanding of how human nature, in terms of values, sentiments, beliefs, influences, individual preferences and decisions across genders and generations should be taken up to reinvent CBA as a nudge as proposed by Cass Sunstein. These values bring important insights for conventional transport planning and assessment tools that are currently based on more simplified set of variables such as travel costs and absolute time savings and reducing traffic congestion .

These values can also be reflected in the public interest. In this report this concept of public interest was also analysed to determine how this it affects EU policies and legislation in the context of mobility and transport. For instance, while a policy change may be in the public interest (e.g., strengthening the rail or inland waterway transport networks through, among others, the TEN-T policy), its execution and success depend on external factors which transcend the interest itself (e.g., competition – or lack thereof – prices, consumer demand, popularity). It appears that the values, sentiments, beliefs, influences, individual preferences and decisions, which can be reflected in a public interest, need to be taken into account in the mobility planning, innovation, appraisal guidelines and legislation.

Our analysis revealed that the concept of public interest is abstract and difficult to describe in an objective manner. Public interest is a concept that needs validation by the legislating authority/body/parliament and becomes determined when juxtaposed with a legal rule. The concept of public interest is not defined as such in EU legislation or jurisprudence. However, public interest is at the core of certain pieces of legislation or at the base of reforms (and policy objectives).

Aside from the role of public interest in legislation, the report also focuses on the role of this concept in the context of the EU's fundamental freedoms, namely how the public interest can be used as an exception

¹⁵³ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/docgener/informat/2014/guidance_urban_mobility.pdf

¹⁵⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/inea/sites/default/files/cba_guide_cohesion_policy.pdf

to limit the applicability these freedom (namely, free movement of persons and of workers, freedom of establishment, free movement of goods), subject to certain limitations. In fact, the public interest exception should not go beyond what is necessary and it should be instrumental to achieve the interest at stake. The public interest exception is therefore a very flexible instrument which can have a significant impact on the transport policy for the future. The concept of public interest is always evolving based on citizens' and the legislator's sensitivities, opinions, interests.

Furthermore, with the fast pace of digitalization and rolling out of emerging mobility systems in European cities, it is essential to update the current appraisal methodology used for transport planning. Incorporating people's wellbeing perspectives and cohorts that share some cluster of specific attributes/values (e.g. welfare attributes, sharing value, environmental values) in current urban mobility planning cycles (ex ante and ex-post) can also support the identification of gaps and requirements for future transport models. In addition, this identification of gaps and requirements can contribute to the development of the decision support tools which could help with the identification of main sources of commuters' satisfaction regarding travel pattern change and promoting multimodal travel behaviour. Short and long-term outcomes of such analysis could also enormously capitalise benefits of human values integration in the mobility value chain for private and public transport sectors in the future mobility.

The consequent elaboration of social justice and human well-being measures could also enhance the policy discussion and mobilise decision-makers and authorities towards selecting the most cost-effective strategies to support inclusive transport policies which can lead to balancing the economy and human values. These values, such as ethics, rationality, sensitivity, morality and prudence, should be coupled with investments to increase the perceived quality of individual travel experience with the aim to overcome transport planning and infrastructure design challenges such as customising mobility services for all citizens. Furthermore, it is also necessary to set out reforms in the current transport appraisal system to align such system with the EU Green Deal objectives, in particular the EU commitment for a 90% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions from transport by 2050, and the PEP "to attract and support investment in environment and health friendly transport".

The shift from an economic to a welfare approach to transport project appraisal has the potential to contribute to the development of information societies with a human nature, as stated by Jana Carp (2014. The Importance of "Slow" for Liveable Cities. Feltrinelli.) who explains this concept well by introducing the Slow City movement, which is a vision for sustainable cities combining pleasure and productivity:

Correlated with digital and transportation technologies, high speed can be an advantage in discrete situations, but it has significant secondary effects that reduce overall quality of life, inhibit personal and public relationship, and exacerbate injury to people and ecosystems. At a time when we face the

unprecedented question of human sustainability, and cities increasingly invest in digital innovations to improve the efficiency of urban systems (the Smart City), certain aspects of speed hinder capacity-building for social and ecological resilience. [...] Good quality of life, and better business results, depend in large part on strategic employment of fast and slow (Davis and Atkinson 2010) . It is not about pace in itself but what pace affords. When fast people slow down, they experience other people, the incidental pleasures of life, the character of the land, the weather, sounds, smells, and tastes. This embodied awareness of place and people is part of what signifies the quality of life promoted by the Slow movement. It is no envisioned as a period of leisure outside work life, but as characteristic of the social and ecological environments in which people live their whole lives.

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